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Muzeul Național al Unirii, Alba Iulia
ICD - Interactions Culturelles et Discursives, Université de Tours
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Si non vis recipere meam fidem et baptismum, exeas regnum meum vel solvas tantum; et quod plus est, te decapitabo:

The Circular Letter of the Bosnian Vicar Bartholomew of La Verna and Repression of the Krstjani in 1459–1460

Paweł Cholewicki

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RÉSUMÉ: L'article analyse l'influence possible d'une lettre circulaire rédigée vers 1378 par le vicaire franciscain Barthélemy de La Verna sur la campagne de baptêmes forcés organisée en Bosnie en 1459 sous le règne du roi Stjepan Tomaš. À la suite de la chute de Smederevo et soumis à de fortes pressions diplomatiques, Tomaš enjoignit aux Krstjani – membres d'une Église bosnienne tenue pour hérétique – d'accepter le baptême ou de quitter le royaume, provoquant, selon Pie II, plusieurs milliers de conversions. L'étude propose d'éclairer cet épisode à la lumière de la doctrine coercitive élaborée par Barthélemy. Figure centrale du vicariat franciscain de Bosnie, Barthélemy formula un ensemble structuré d'arguments destinés à convaincre les autorités séculières de soutenir un vaste programme de baptêmes et à en affirmer la légitimité théologique et juridique. Enraciné dans l'Écriture, la tradition patristique et divers précédents historiques, ce cadre doctrinal visait à orienter les campagnes de conversion entreprises par la couronne hongroise au XIV^e siècle. L'article montre que cette lettre circulait encore au XV^e siècle dans les milieux franciscains du vicariat bosnien, ce qui rend plausible son impact sur la politique religieuse de Tomaš. Les parallèles sont nombreux : recours à un baptême imposé sans période d'instruction préalable, affirmation du devoir des seigneurs de garantir l'orthodoxie religieuse, rôle central attribué aux Franciscains dans la mise en œuvre du programme. Autant d'éléments que l'on retrouve dans les mesures prises par Tomaš en 1459. L'auteur suggère ainsi que le roi, soucieux de rétablir sa position auprès de la papauté, a pu mobiliser la doctrine coercitive de Barthélemy pour justifier une opération de conversion à grande échelle. L'article se conclut par une nouvelle transcription du texte latin, établie à partir de la confrontation d'une ancienne édition avec un témoin manuscrit, ainsi que par une traduction anglaise intégrale, fournissant des instruments renouvelés pour l'étude des relations entre catholiques et orthodoxes au Moyen Âge.

MOTS-CLÉS: Franciscains; Bosnie médiévale; royaume hongrois; conversion forcée; Barthélemy de La Verna.

REZUMAT: Articolul analizează influența posibilă a unei scrisori circulare redactate în jurul anului 1378 de vicarul franciscan Bartolomeu din La Verna asupra campaniei de botezuri forțate organizate în Bosnia în 1459, sub domnia regelui Stjepan Tomaš. În urma căderii orașului Smederevo și a unor presiuni diplomatice intense, Tomaš le-a ordonat *Krstjani*-lor (membri ai unei Biserici bosniace considerate eretice) să accepte botezul sau să părăsească regatul, ceea ce a dus, potrivit lui Pius al II-lea, la câteva mii de convertiri. Studiul propune ca acest episod să fie reinterpretat în lumina doctrinei coercitive elaborate de Bartolomeu. Figură centrală a vicariatului franciscan din Bosnia, Bartolomeu a formulat un set coerent de argumente menite să convingă autoritățile seculare să sprijine un program amplu de botezuri și să îi întemeieze legitimitatea teologică și juridică. Bazată pe Scriptură, pe tradiția patristică și pe diverse precedente istorice, această construcție doctrinară urmărea să orienteze campaniile de convertire inițiate de coroana maghiară în secolul al XIV-lea. Articolul arată că această scrisoare circula încă în secolul al XV-lea în mediile franciscane ale vicariatului bosniac, ceea ce face verosimilă influența ei asupra politicii religioase a lui Tomaš. Paralelele sunt numeroase: recurgerea la botezul impus fără o perioadă prealabilă de instruire, afirmarea obligației nobililor de a garanta conformitatea religioasă, rolul central atribuit franciscanilor în implementarea programului – toate aceste elemente se regăsesc în măsurile adoptate de Tomaš în 1459. Autorul sugerează astfel că regele, dornic să-și recâștige statutul în fața papalității, ar fi putut utiliza doctrina coercitivă a lui Bartolomeu pentru a legitima o operațiune de convertire de mare amploare. Articolul se încheie cu o transcriere nouă a textului latin, realizată prin confruntarea unei ediții vechi cu un martor manuscris, precum și cu o traducere integrală în limba engleză, oferind instrumente noi pentru studiul relațiilor dintre catolici și ortodocși în Evul Mediu.

CUVINTE-CHEIE: franciscani; Bosnia medievală; regatul maghiar; convertire forțată; Bartolomeu din La Verna.

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◀ *The fifteenth-century funerary monument of Vukosav Lupcic from the Dolovi-Poljice necropolis on Mount Visočica, one of two known medieval funerary monuments inscribed with medieval Bosnian Cyrillic texts.* Source: Wikipedia / Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 3.0 Unported license.

In 1459, shortly after the surrender of Smederevo to the Turks on 20 June that year, the penultimate king of Bosnia, Stjepan Tomaš, presented all the ‘Manichaeans’ in his realm with a choice: to accept baptism or face expulsion. Pius II reported in his *Commentaries* that approximately 12,000 individuals were baptised, while forty remained resolute and fled to Duke Stjepan Kosača, referred to as their ‘comrade in perfidy’. Three heretics were taken to Rome, where they renounced their faith in a public ceremony. A few years later, a high-ranking member of that group, Gost Radin, petitioned the Venetian authorities to allow *him* and ‘fifty or sixty’ individuals from his ‘sect’ to enter their territory. These accounts represent some of the final historical references to the religious community or order known as the Bosnian Church. The *Krstjani*, meaning ‘Christians’, who formed this community, did not submit to either Rome or Constantinople, and were accused by the two ‘great Churches’ of adhering to a heretical belief in two principles, commonly referred to today as Dualism. King Tomaš’s decision to abandon the tolerant stance of his predecessors in favour of repression has drawn considerable scholarly attention. Historians have examined the causes and consequences of the campaign, the king’s motivations, papal oversight, the timeline of the persecution, its scope and character, as well as the numbers reported by Pius II.¹ Unsurprisingly, the sources examined have been primarily contemporary with the events, with little or no attention given to earlier writings. However, nearly a century prior, the long-serving Franciscan vicar of Bosnia, Bartholomew of La Verna, issued a letter in which he justified the use of coercion in campaigns of baptism of large groups of non-Catholic population. He described a hypothetical scenario in which a king offers his subject the choice to be baptised, pay a certain sum, go into exile, or be executed, evoking the fate that had befallen the *Krstjani*.

This paper starts by examining the roots of the heresy in Bosnia, outlining the development of the Bosnian Church, the competing historiographical interpretations of its doctrinal character, and its unique place in the religious and political landscape of medieval Bosnia. From this, the study turns to the foundation of the Franciscan Bosnian vicariate and to the tenure and writings of Bartholomew of La Verna. A central section of the paper is dedicated to an analysis of Bartholomew’s circular letter and its interpretation of the 1378 papal bull *Devotionis sinceritas*, which encouraged coercion in matters of faith. Finally, the letter’s rhetorical strategies and practical instructions are examined also for their potential afterlife in shaping the ideological and operational framework of the 1459 campaign. I will consider the relationship between Bartholomew’s thought and the measures adopted by the Bosnian royal court almost a century later, suggesting that the letter may have served as a conceptual and justificatory model for the Franciscans involved in organising the mass baptism campaign. The paper aims to uncover how the letter may have informed one of the most significant episodes of the Bosnian Middle Ages (Fig. 1).

▼ Fig. 1. Drawing of *ms Basel*, Öffentliche Bibliothek der Universität Basel, A vi 15, fol. 91v (detail).

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*Quiluo qd violata gencionalis verbi qd ut cu ali
cu pponitur talis gduo Bimo us r d r i p e meam fidem qd bapaf
mi exeat regnu meu ul soluas tm*

Tam ecclesia quam diocesis Bosnensis, quae ad Romanam ecclesiam nullo medio pertinet. The Bosnian Diocese’s Lapse to Heresy

To understand the potential impact of Bartholomew’s letter on events in 1459, it is first necessary to present the context of heresy in Bosnia and the place it occupies in its religious and political landscape. From 1199 until the mid-thirteenth century, the Roman curia received numerous reports suggesting that heretical groups had settled in Bosnia, spreading their beliefs among the local population and securing the patronage of the ban.² In a letter dated 21 November 1202, Pope Innocent III associated these groups with the Cathars.³ The creed of the Cathars was based on a belief in two opposing forces—good and evil—represented by God and Satan, both regarded as creators. The ‘good’ God was believed to have created all spiritual beings, while Satan, identified with Jehovah of the Old Testament, was said to have created the material world ‘in six days’. This dualist conception of creation had far-reaching theological implications for the broader doctrinal system, which has been the subject of extensive historiographical analysis.⁴

A range of measures was undertaken by the papacy to eradicate heresy in Bosnia. These included the deployment of papal legates, the securing of abjurations, and the establishment of agreements with the Bosnian bans.⁵ The Dominican friars also played a role in this effort, first being mentioned in connection with Bosnia in a source dated 10 October 1233.⁶ The papacy also directed its attention toward the Bosnian bishopric, which it suspected of being complicit in the spread of heresy. On 5 June 1232, Pope Gregory IX issued a letter to the archbishop of Kalocsa and the bishop of Zagreb, outlining a series of serious allegations against an unnamed bishop of Bosnia. This included neglect of pastoral responsibilities and, potentially, active support for the heretics.⁷ The papal legate in Hungary, James of Pecoraria, reportedly found the bishop guilty of at least some of the charges.⁸

By the end of 1233, the bishop of Bosnia was replaced with the Dominican friar John of Wildeshausen, who would later become Master of the Order of Preachers.⁹ This replacement appears to have triggered considerable social unrest, prompting a crusade from Hungary to secure the success of the new bishop’s efforts against heresy.¹⁰ The crusade was led by Duke Coloman in 1237–1238, and he occupied the majority of the Bosnian banate’s territories.¹¹ The Dominicans cooperated with Coloman, restoring a number of churches, undertaking efforts to convert the heretics, and handing over many of those who remained unrepentant to be burned.¹² However, the crusade’s progress was abruptly nullified by the Mongol invasion of Hungary; Duke Coloman was fatally wounded at the Battle of Muhi on 11 April 1241. This phase of intensified papal intervention came to an end on 27 March 1248, when Pope Innocent IV forbade further military action in Bosnia until the faith of the ban could be re-evaluated.¹³ The outcome of this investigation remains unknown, but no substantial attempt to resolve the problem of Bosnian heresy through military means was undertaken until the following century.

The archdiocese of Dubrovnik was blamed for tolerating the Bosnian bishopric’s descent into heresy.¹⁴ The archbishop of Kalocsa was appointed metropolitan of Bosnia, following a papal bull dated 28 August 1247. The bull declared that: ‘the Bosnian Church, along with its diocese, no longer belonged to the Roman Church, hav-

ing fully embraced the faithlessness of heretical depravity, because its sins condemned it'.¹⁵ Subsequently, the Bosnian bishop established his permanent seat at Đakovo in the kingdom of Hungary (present-day Croatia) by May 1252. Đakovo remained the 'canonical' seat of the Bosnian bishopric until modern times. In effect, the Cyrillo-Methodian form of Christianity in Bosnia—supervised until the early 1230s by the Catholic *Ecclesia Bosnensis* under the jurisdiction of the archdiocese of Dubrovnik—was severed from the Roman Church following the bishopric's relocation to Đakovo.¹⁶ In its place, a new religious structure gradually emerged, first referred to in a charter dated 1326/1329 as the Bosnian Church (*Crkva bosanska*).¹⁷ Although condemned by both of the 'great Churches', the Bosnian Church was tolerated by Bosnian rulers until 1459, when its members were presented with the choice of baptism or expulsion.

As an indigenous phenomenon, the Bosnian Church has become something of a beacon of both scholarly and popular fascination in South Slavic countries, especially in Bosnia and Hercegovina. Its historiography is extensive, yet it remains deeply divided over the question of its doctrinal character. The study of the Bosnian Church is complicated by the inherent challenges of researching medieval dualist movements, compounded by the entrenchment of national historiographical traditions. Scholars such as Jaroslav Šidak, Pejo Čošković, and Dženan Dautović have made notable efforts to bring some structure to this highly complex field.¹⁸ Academic interpretations can broadly be categorised into three frameworks: the '[Eastern] Orthodox framework' (*Pravoslavni okvir*), the 'dualist framework' (*Dualistički okvir*), and the 'orthodox framework' (*Pravovjerni okvir*). The [Eastern] Orthodox framework maintains that the Bosnian Church was essentially Eastern Orthodox in nature, comparable to the churches of Serbia and Bulgaria.¹⁹ The dualist framework, by contrast, holds that the Bosnian Church formed part of the wider 'neo-Manichean movement' of the high Middle Ages, comprising communities displaced by persecution elsewhere.²⁰ Some post-war historians within this framework argued instead that the Catholic *Ecclesia Bosnensis*, having lapsed into dualism, evolved into the heretical Bosnian Church, with its leader—the *Djed*—continuing the lineage of 'canonical' bishops that had existed prior to the appointment of John of Wildeshausen.²¹ Finally, the orthodox framework also traces the origins of the Bosnian Church to the *Ecclesia Bosnensis* after its separation from Rome, but contends that it remained doctrinally orthodox and was never 'contaminated' by dualist beliefs.²²

After the prominent Serbian historian Sima Ćirković adopted the dualist framework, the '[Eastern] Orthodox framework' declined in popularity, leaving the dualist and orthodox frameworks as the dominant positions in contemporary scholarship.²³ Catholic and Orthodox sources—including anti-heretical polemics, lists of errors, abjuration texts, condemnations issued by Serbian synods, and various letters—provide abundant evidence accusing the Bosnian Church of holding beliefs commonly associated with the Cathars and Bogomils. These sources frequently refer to its adherents as 'the heretics of Bosnia', 'the Patarenes', 'the Manicheans', or 'the Babuni' (*Бабуну*).²⁴ However, such sources are often considered unreliable, and scholars tend to focus instead on the comparatively limited material produced by the Bosnian Church itself. Proponents of the dualist framework frequently cite the glosses found in Bosnian biblical manuscripts as indica-

tive of dualist interpretations of particular passages, and they also highlight the prayer formulations in the Radosav manuscript as corresponding to the *consolamentum* of the Cathars.²⁵ Conversely, advocates of the orthodox framework dispute and deconstruct any identifications of dualism within these sources, which they argue display no evidence of dualist belief. They often cite the testament of *Gost Radin*, dated 5 January 1466, which contains numerous contradictions to the accusations made in polemical literature against the Bosnian heretics.²⁶

The Bosnian Church was organised as a religious community or order with a clearly defined hierarchy. This structure has become a subject of scholarly debate, particularly regarding whether it more closely resembled an Orthodox monastic community or the organisation of the Cathar churches.²⁷ The head of the Church was known as the *Djed*, after whom were the *Strojníci*, who were themselves divided into higher ranked *Gosti* and lower ranked *Starci*.²⁸ The remainder of the order's members were referred to in vernacular sources as *Krstjani*, meaning 'Christians', while some Latin sources described them as *religiosi*. The term *Krstjani* has caused some interpretative ambiguity, as it may also have referred to 'lay' believers; however, it appears that members of this religious community claimed exclusive use of the term 'Christians' for themselves.²⁹ Although some elements of their hierarchical structure bear resemblance to those of contemporary orthodox or heterodox communities, the religious organisation of the *Krstjani* appears to have been, on the whole, genuinely original.³⁰ Regardless of the precise nature of the Bosnian Church's creed, the *Krstjani* were deeply embedded in the social fabric of medieval Bosnia. They held positions of trust, frequently appearing as guarantors in vernacular charters, and even the Republic of Ragusa tolerated their religious dissent due to their recognised value as mediators.³¹

Ut omnes ecclesiae, quae nunc inibi jacent dirutae et destructae, auxiliante Deo in pristinum statum resurgent:
Mission and Scope of the Franciscan Bosnian Vicariate

While the development of the Bosnian Church reveals an unusual religious landscape confronting the medieval papacy, the Franciscan Order emerged as the Church's principal agent for addressing the persistence of heresy. For approximately a century, Bosnia was without any formal Catholic ecclesiastical structure, and the regular Church hierarchy and diocesan system were not restored until 1881, following the Austro-Hungarian occupation of the country. Nevertheless, the Order of Friars Minor appears to have shown an early interest in expanding its activities into Bosnia. Some individual friars may have been active in parts of its territory during the early 1290s and mid-1320s, but nothing certain is known about their activities.³² The fourteenth century witnessed significant territorial expansion by the Kingdom of Hungary, which channelled its ambitions towards its weaker Orthodox neighbours in the southeast.³³ The Hungarian monarchy recognised that the conversion of local elites and populations to Catholicism would greatly facilitate its political and cultural influence in these parts. In 1339, the minister general of the Franciscan Order, Geraldus Odonis, travelled to Hungary, where King Charles Robert invited him to visit Bosnia. He was reportedly warmly received by Ban Stjepan II, and following consultations, the minister

general resolved to establish the Franciscan Bosnian vicariate. This foundation was confirmed by the general chapter at Assisi in 1340. The vicariate represented a structure in which the minister general exercised more direct authority than in a standard Franciscan province. Unlike provincial ministers, vicars were appointed directly by the minister general rather than elected by a local chapter. Initially, the Bosnian vicariate was administered by foreign friars, although by the fifteenth century, native Franciscans had become increasingly prominent.³⁴

Although termed the Bosnian vicariate, its jurisdiction quickly extended beyond the borders of the medieval Bosnian state. As early as 1347, it was authorised to establish convents in Ston and Đakovo.³⁵ King Louis I actively involved the Bosnian vicariate in the advancement of his political ambitions.³⁶ The Chronicle of the Twenty-Four Generals recounts that, following the conquest of the 'Tsardom of Vidin' in 1365 and setting up of the Hungarian banate under Benedict Himfi in its place, eight friars from the vicariate were assigned to assist with the Catholicisation and administration of baptisms of the population. Furthermore, on 20 July 1366, the king ordered that the Orthodox Slavic priests with their families from counties of Caraş and Kovin were to be brought to the same Benedict for examination, and they were converted and baptised likely by the Franciscans.³⁷ It appears as though the decision targeted mainly the Serbian clergy who took refuge in Banat.³⁸ It has also been argued that, in the same year, Louis I issued a discriminatory charter against his Orthodox subjects, restricting landholding in the Caransebeş district to Catholic nobles alone.³⁹ In the summer of 1368, friars John of Reno and Andrew of Perugia reported to Avignon that the Franciscans had converted 'many thousands' of individuals across Bulgaria, Serbia, and Bosnia.⁴⁰ In 1369, five friars were martyred during the Bulgarian recapture of Vidin.⁴¹

Franciscan tradition further credits Louis with the foundation of several Bosnian convents in Banat, situated between the Tisza and Danube rivers on the southern frontier of the kingdom. *De conformitate vitae B. Francisci* by Bartholomew of Pisa, along with the Hungarian Observant Chronicle, list numerous convents belonging to the vicariate in Hungary that had been established by the end of the fourteenth century in Đakovo, Varoš (Alsán), Drobeta-Turnu Severin (Szörény), Orşova (Orsova), Caransebeş (Karánsebes), Cseri (likely present-day Sacoşu Turcesc, Romania), Bocşa Română (Kövesd), Vidin (Видин), Kovin (Keve), Banatska Palanka (Haram), Armeniş (Ermény, in the Caraş river valley, somewhere in the Banatska Subotica area) and Ineu (Jenő).⁴² This network illustrates the significant presence of the Bosnian vicariate in southern parts of Hungary where the parish infrastructure was poorly developed and where the Orthodox Church retained considerable influence.

Serving in the vicariate presented a range of challenges for its friars. Not long after its establishment, vicars began reporting a shortage of manpower to meet the demands of their mission. Additional difficulties included restrictions on the elderly and infirm returning to their home provinces, the severe austerity of the convents, and the hardships associated with collecting sufficient alms for their sustenance. Opportunities for education and theological instruction were extremely limited, and the friars often faced hostility from local heretics, the Orthodox population, and the Turks. Furthermore, there was consider-

able uncertainty surrounding their rights to administer the sacraments and provide pastoral care in places lacking an established ecclesiastical structure.⁴³

Per sollicitas et continuas fratrum dicti ordinis in eadem vicaria existentium predicationes et inductiones quingenta milia personarum infidelium [...] ad orthodoxe fidei sinceritatem unanimiter [...] conversa fore noscantur.
The Vicariate of Bartholomew of La Verna

It fell to the vicars of Bosnia to address these challenges in order to ensure that the vicariate fulfilled its spiritual mission and continued to expand the boundaries of the faith. One of the aims behind the vicariate's extension into Dalmatia and Hungary was to guarantee the economic stability of the houses in Bosnia and to secure a steady influx of friars to assist in its administration.⁴⁴ The vicars also petitioned the papacy for various privileges that would facilitate the administration of the sacraments and resolve uncertainties regarding their application. The vicariate of Bartholomew of La Verna stands out as especially pivotal.⁴⁵ He was first recorded as vicar of Bosnia in 1367 and appeared in further documents from the years 1368, 1372, 1373, 1376, 1380, 1392, 1394, 1395, 1400, 1402, and 1404.⁴⁶ He is also presumed to have held office at some point between December 1406 and November 1408, as his petition from that period is mentioned in a later source.⁴⁷ This amounts to an exceptionally long, albeit not continuous, tenure. It is known that the general chapter at Aquila in 1376 sent Bartholomew to the Holy Land.⁴⁸ Mandić has dated Bartholomew's vicariate to the periods 1366–1375 and 1378–1408, while admitting uncertainty for the years 1381–1390 when evidence is lacking. This timeframe is generally accepted by South Slavic literature.⁴⁹ Although the precise dating remains subject to debate, it is evident that Bartholomew held the office for an unusually long time and was an active and influential figure throughout.⁵⁰

Bartholomew appears to have played a key role in Franciscan proselytising efforts, which unfolded alongside the anti-Orthodox policies of King Louis I in Bulgaria and Banat—through which the vicar likely became more closely acquainted with the monarch.⁵¹ At the king's request, the pope authorised the vicar of Bosnia, by a bull issued on 16 June 1372, to be granted two sites within the domain of Nikola Altomanović in Serbia, one in the region of Glaz on the border between Bosnia and Hungary, and as many as nine more across Bosnia, Serbia, and Wallachia.⁵² Bartholomew's ambitions extended further. He petitioned for permission to establish convents 'around Caransebeş and Greater Wallachia', as well as in Varoš and Krbava, with the aim of extending pastoral care specifically to 'the schismatic Vlachs, some of whom live in pastures and tents, tending the flocks and herds with which they abound, yet no one takes care about preaching or converting them'.⁵³ In response, the pope issued a bull on 1 June 1373, allowing the establishment of up to six convents in such areas.⁵⁴ Later, in 1400, following the devastation caused by the Turkish incursions, Bartholomew was authorised to receive one convent on Ragusan territory, one in Hungary, one on the island of Korčula, and 'one other in a place that you would consider appropriate for refuge and protection'.⁵⁵ He was also the vicar responsible for extending the reach of the vicariate across the Adriatic to southern Italy, where he was granted convents in Galatina (1391) and Cortone (1400), thereby facilitating the

movement of friars from Latin Christian lands into the Balkans.⁵⁶ In a letter dated 7 March 1402, the pope commended Bartholomew after the vicar reported that ‘five hundred thousand persons of the infidel population [...] have been unanimously converted to the sincerity of the orthodox faith’.⁵⁷ Although this figure has been debated and challenged by scholars—who argue that the Franciscans were prone to exaggerating their success—it should be noted, as will be explored later in this paper, that this number includes not only those won over through preaching and example but also individuals baptised under compulsion.

Bartholomew was required to ensure that his subordinates had the appropriate rights to administer the sacraments in areas where ecclesiastical structures were either non-existent or underdeveloped—an issue that had already been reported as problematic in 1347.⁵⁸ On 28 January 1369, the pope extended to the friars of the Bosnian vicariate the privileges of the bull *Cum hora undecima*, originally issued in 1235 and subsequently reissued on several occasions. This bull granted full remission of sins to any friar departing for the lands of the ‘infidels’ to preach Christ. It also authorised them to administer all the sacraments without requiring permission or consultation from bishops, to absolve penitents even if bound by excommunication, and to preach and interact freely with non-Catholics—all with the aim of facilitating the spread of the faith in non-Catholic territories.⁵⁹ A further bull, dated 13 December 1369, allowed the friars of the Bosnian vicariate to collect alms in Hungary, Dalmatia, and Croatia, as sufficient alms could not be secured within Bosnia alone.⁶⁰ A bull *Devotionis sinceritas* issued on 22 December 1378, commissioned the friars to ‘persuade and exhort the secular lords of those parts to compel their subjects and vassals, under threat of bodily punishment or monetary fine, to obey the commands of the Church and of the friars in matters concerning the salvation of souls and the advancement of the Catholic faith’.⁶¹ This explicitly encouraged the friars to enlist and instrumentalise the authority of secular rulers in order to ensure the Catholic policies through coercive means. Bartholomew’s circular letter—referred to in the title of this article—is devoted entirely to interpreting this passage of the bull, a subject which will be examined in detail later. The bull also contained other grants, including permission to any confessor to grant full absolution of sins to those on their deathbed.

Pastoral care and administration of sacraments across the religiously and socially diverse landscape of the Bosnian vicariate inevitably gave rise to ambiguities concerning certain Church regulations. In 1372, through his envoy to the Avignon curia, Berengar of Aragon, Bartholomew submitted twenty-three questions—each representing a real or hypothetical case that the Franciscans had found perplexing or for which they sought papal endorsement to support their existing practices. In response, Pope Gregory XI issued a bull on 22 June 1372 establishing a theological commission under the supervision of Gaufridus Lemarhec, bishop of Quimper, to examine the submitted queries.⁶² The set of responses was completed in 1373 and is preserved in a miscellaneous manuscript held in the archives of the Croatian Academy of Sciences and Arts in Zagreb (*Miscellanea theologica* I. a 57). The document is known as *Dubia ecclesiastica Fratris Bartholomaei Vicarii Generalis in Bosnia submissa Gregorio XI Pontifici Romano et responsa ecclesiae Romanae ad eundem de anno 1373*.⁶³ This source provides valuable insight into the religious and social conditions of the lands in which

the friars of the vicariate operated and has, accordingly, attracted considerable scholarly interest.⁶⁴

The submitted questions primarily concern the administration of the sacraments, including six related to marriage and three to baptism.⁶⁵ The elevated social status of members of the Bosnian Church presented particular challenges, prompting Bartholomew to inquire whether the sacraments could be administered in the presence of patrons of heretics, whether laypeople were allowed to engage in theological discussion with heretics, and how to respond when a convert to Catholicism continued to ‘adore’ the heretics and observe their rites ‘with the mouth rather than the heart’. Other questions addressed issues arising in areas under Orthodox influence. For example, Bartholomew asked whether the consecration of chrism and the Eucharist by Orthodox priests was valid, and whether a priest who converted from the schism should be re-ordained. One question considered the status of those described as ‘simple among the Greeks, unaware of the Greek schism yet professing belief in Christ’. Could such people be saved ‘so long as they are baptised, or firmly believe themselves to be baptised’, and should they be left undisturbed, or rather drawn away from their priests and former customs?⁶⁶ These questions clearly reflect the complexity of the pastoral situations encountered by the Franciscans—cases that presented a challenge to the existing ecclesiastical legislation and that would not have arisen in the more uniform religious landscape of Latin Christendom. Several of these issues would also reappear in Bartholomew’s other writings (Fig. 2).

As the head of the Bosnian vicariate, Bartholomew was evidently concerned that the number of friars under his authority was insufficient to meet the ambitious challenges ahead. Berengar of Aragon had also secured a papal bull dated 22 June 1372, which urged all Franciscan superiors to send to Bosnia any friars—whether ordained or lay—who were willing to undertake a mission against heresy, and the vicar was allowed to accept up to sixty individuals.⁶⁷ The bull *Devotionis sinceritas* from 22 December 1378, authorised Bartholomew to receive up to thirty additional friars and clarified that any friar who had previously returned from the vicariate was allowed to travel there a second time. It also stipulated that secular priests who came to the vicariate to assist the friars in their work were to enjoy the remission of sins granted by *Cum hora undecima* and to retain their rights to income from their home ecclesiastical benefices.⁶⁸

Such efforts to address the shortage of manpower did not suggest that Bartholomew was willing to compromise on the quality of religious conduct. As the bull from 22 June 1372 specified, he required individuals who were ‘suitable in judgment, way of life, and moral character’. Earlier, on 13 December 1368, he had been granted a bull authorising him to return any friar deemed unfit for service in the vicariate to their home province. He was even allowed to send away friars of the Bosnian nation if he judged them to be of no use.⁶⁹ The vicar clearly recognised the potential of those with exemplary religious discipline to attract ‘unbelievers’ to the faith, while remaining acutely aware of the danger posed by those of disreputable conduct, whose behaviour risked causing scandal.

On 1 August 1377, in the Holy Land, Bartholomew, together with seven other friars, issued statutes for the Franciscans then residing there, comprising eighteen articles.⁷⁰ These statutes prohibited friars from accepting gold, sil-

▲ Fig. 1. Drawing of MS Zagreb, AHAZU, I a 57, fol. 77r.

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▼ Fig. 2. Drawing of MS Zagreb, AHAZU, I a 57, fol. 78v.

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ver, or other precious objects for private use; they set out very specific conditions under which money could be accepted, acknowledging that it was impossible to maintain these places without financial support. They also forbade women from entering male convents, prohibited friars from visiting women's convents unaccompanied, and regulated the observance of fasts and the reception of pilgrims. In tone and content, these statutes reflected the spirit of the 'reformed' Franciscan constitutions.⁷¹ Bartholomew's approach has led many scholars to regard him as a representative of the Observant reform movement within the Franciscan Order.⁷² However, such an identification is problematic, given that he lived prior to the formal division of the Order into the Observant and Conventual branches. That said, it was during his vicariate that the followers of Paoluccio of Foligno first established contact with Bosnia.⁷³ Overall, Bartholomew may be characterised as a reform-minded superior: one who established links with hermit-reformers, maintained strict discipline among his subordinates, fought heresy and schism, and drew inspiration from the more reformed strands of Franciscan legislation.

Oves errantes, quae non solum vocibus sed flagellis ad ovile veri pastoris reduci habent:
Writings of Bartholomew of La Verna

Bartholomew is known to us not only through his leadership but also through his writings, which offer invaluable insight into his theological outlook and pastoral strategy. Some scholars have attributed to him the authorship of *Isti sunt errores hereticorum Bosnensium*, a list of the errors of the Bosnian heretics found immediately after *Dubia ecclesiastica* in the same manuscript.⁷⁴ This attribution is problematic, although Bartholomew's authorship cannot be definitively ruled out.⁷⁵ The same treaty, with minor variations, is also preserved in the Biblioteca Marciana in Venice.⁷⁶ The text itself is a rather concise list of thirty-two errors of dualism ascribed to the Bosnian heretics. As György Galamb has demonstrated, *Isti sunt errores* were influenced by the treatise *Disputatio inter catholicum et paterinum hereticum* from the early thirteenth century, attributed to a certain *Georgius laicus* and widely circulat-

ed in Dominican circles.⁷⁷ Given the structural parallels, *Isti sunt errores* may be considered an extract of the *Disputatio*, though it should be noted that certain themes are absent—such as the Patarens' condemnation of prayers for the dead or their claim that miracles of the saints are the work of the devil—while others represent additions to the *Disputatio's* text, such as the assertion that the Virgin Mary is an angel rather than human, that the heretics consider themselves the true Church (with one regarded as the vicar of Christ and a successor of St Peter), or their rejection of the Catholic sacraments.⁷⁸ It is possible that the older text was supplemented and adapted by Bartholomew (or another Bosnian friar) on the basis of his own observations. A work that is clearly misattributed to Bartholomew is the *Tractatus quomodo debemus nos ponere ad recipiendum corpus Christi*, which seems to be nothing more than St Bonaventure's *De praeparatione ad missam*.⁷⁹

Three writings preserved in a manuscript held at the University Library of Basel (UB Basel, A VI 15) appear to be attributable to Bartholomew: *Septem suppositiones et rationes processione Spiritus Sancti ex Patre Filioque*, *Errores schismaticorum orientalium*, and *Epistula fratribus Vicarie Bosne*. All three seem to form a distinct nucleus within the manuscript, and they are interrelated in content. While the first two texts are anonymous, the third is clearly authored by Bartholomew.⁸⁰ The first treatise presents seven theological arguments in support of the procession of the Holy Spirit from both the Father and the Son. The second outlines ten doctrinal and liturgical errors—labelled 'heresies'—attributed to the Serbs, Bulgarians, and Vlachs within the kingdom of Hungary.⁸¹ While some of the points reflect standard doctrinal divergences between Orthodoxy and Catholicism, others appear more original, suggesting that they could be based on direct observations made by the Franciscans of the vicariate in the field.

The Orthodox were accused of having forgotten the rite of baptism 'some because of stubbornness, others because of contacts they have with the Paulicians of Wallachia or Patarens of Bosnia, and others because they are not among the pastors appointed by their superiors — Roman or Hungarian bishops'.⁸² Their priests apparently did not use a standardised baptismal formula containing the essential invocation of the Trinity; instead, each said what he considered appropriate when pouring the water, such as 'blessed are they [whose iniquities are forgiven, and whose sins are covered]' (Ps 31:1), or 'you will sprinkle me [with hyssop, and I shall be cleansed; you will wash me, and I shall be made whiter than snow] (Ps 50:7), or '[therefore] as many of you have been baptised [in Christ], are clothed with Christ' (Gal 3:27), or 'alleluia' three times, or 'the servant of God is baptized in the name of Saint Peter or Demetrius', depending on the name they wished to give.⁸³ It was claimed that barely two in twenty priests agreed on the same formula, and considerable confusion surrounded the rite.⁸⁴ They also insisted that only priests were authorised to baptise, and refused to baptise infants before the eighth day—even if the child was in danger of death. Remarks on chrism appear to relate specifically to the practices of Orthodox priests in Vidin. Their chrism was said to be some twenty years old and composed of twenty herbs. It could only be blessed by the patriarch, but when supplies were low, they reportedly extended it by mixing in lard, marrow, or hemp oil.

Bartholomew was also appalled by the manner in which

the Orthodox consecrated the body of Christ. The eucharistic bread was referred to as *Brasansa* (*Brašance*) by the Serbs and Bosnians, and as *Komka* by the Bulgarians and Vlachs.⁸⁵ They consecrated it, using phrase: ‘he was led like a sheep to the slaughter, [and like a lamb before its shearer is silent, so he did not open his mouth]’ (Isaiah 53:7), while over wine, they said ‘and one of the soldiers pierced his side with a lance, and immediately there came out blood and water’ (John 19:34), which differed from the words of consecration used by the Latin mass. Furthermore, it was reported that the faithful were instructed to prostrate themselves in worship before the consecration, but not after it. The Vlachs were said to press grapes into the wine, while others diluted the wine excessively with water, or used pure wine without any water at all. Some even mixed the wine with beer, mead, or herbs. All of these practices stood in contrast to Latin liturgical norms, which strictly forbade mixing the eucharistic wine with anything other than a small amount of water.

The *Epistula fratribus Vicarie Bosne* is undated, but it addresses the interpretation of the previously mentioned bull of 22 December 1378 (*Devotionis sinceritas*), and must therefore have been written by Bartholomew shortly after its issuance. The letter focuses exclusively on the article concerning the summoning of friars to persuade and urge secular lords to compel their subjects and vassals to obey the Church in matters of faith. Bartholomew makes it clear that the bull was issued in support of King Louis’s campaigns to baptise the Orthodox population, as well as to endorse his discriminatory policies intended to pressure his vassals into converting to Catholicism.⁸⁶ It appears that some individuals were either negligent in carrying out these measures or openly critical of them. Bartholomew, therefore, composed this letter to clarify the intentions of the bull, justify its provisions, and assist in convincing those reluctant to implement them. The letter is structured around four *inductiva*: namely, reason, nature, scripture, and example—the first of which is the most extensive (Fig. 4).

The letter laments that, due to ‘rusticity and ignorance’, the Orthodox clergy of the Slavs and Vlachs had lost both the knowledge and proper practice of the sacramental rites—particularly that of baptism—and were thus leading their nations towards damnation. Bartholomew even recalled a remark allegedly made by the Byzantine Emperor John V, who was present at Louis’s court in 1366: ‘The king did the right thing to baptise these Slavs, because they follow neither the Greek nor the Roman rite’.⁸⁷ The contempt voiced by the emperor was likely reflective of contemporary tensions with the Serbian tsardom and its autocephalous Patriarchate of Peć, which the Byzantines did not recognise until 1375.⁸⁸ Bartholomew does not appear to object to the Greek rite itself, but rather to what he perceived as its negligent and improper practice. He acknowl-

▼ Fig. 4. Drawing of MS Basel, Öffentliche Bibliothek der Universität Basel, A VI 15, fol. 91r (detail).

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▲ Fig. 5. Drawing of MS Basel, Öffentliche Bibliothek der Universität Basel, A VI 15, fol. 93r (detail).

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edged that some monks from Mount Athos had attempted to instruct the local clergy in the correct rites, but they were too few in number to change his overall assessment. The Slavs and Vlachs therefore needed to be baptised even if they claimed to have already received the sacrament, since the validity of their baptism could not be verified.⁸⁹ He believed that they were otherwise easy to convert and did not require additional probation to faith prior to baptism, as their simple belief in the Trinity was deemed sufficient.⁹⁰ They were compared to ‘the wandering sheep, who must be brought back to the fold of the true shepherd not only by voices but also by whips’ (Fig. 5).⁹¹

Bartholomew was indeed not hesitant to advocate the use of coercive measures, provided they fell within what he termed ‘conditional violence’, as opposed to ‘absolute’ violence. This distinction meant that, before any act of force was inflicted, a condition had to be presented to the individual concerned—for example: accept baptism, pay a certain sum, go into exile, or face execution. Throughout his letter, Bartholomew repeatedly asserts that such measures were both necessary and spiritually beneficial. Even if a person were coerced into baptism and thus received the sacrament merely in appearance—since an unwilling recipient would not receive the grace of the sacrament—Bartholomew maintained that either they or their descendants might eventually accept the faith. This, he argued, would always be a positive outcome and was, in his view, consistent with the way great nations had been converted in the past. Should secular lords prove reluctant to implement such measures, preferring instead to rely on ‘word and example’, they were to be reminded that they served as ministers of God, responsible for punishing the wicked and rewarding the good. They were therefore obliged to uphold the laws concerning the eradication of heresy and schism. Bartholomew added: ‘but as for the claim that the apostles and other saints did not convert the world in this manner by inflicting violence, but baptized those proven in the faith, I reply that our times are different from that. Distinguish the times, and you will be in agreement with the Scriptures!’⁹² The vicar situated such measures within the broader framework of salvation history:

For although the apostles sowed the word of salvation throughout the world, yet because of the persecution of pagan tyrants, that seed could not grow to full conversion and the stability of the Holy Church until the Lord turned the hearts of kings under the yoke of faith. Thus, [the Lord converted] the Latins and Greeks through Constantine; through Charlemagne, the Germans and Teutons, and through Saint King Stephen, he converted the Hungarians, certainly not only by word but also by the sword and hard battles—although they were not heretics or schismatics but complete pagans. In the same way, through Louis, the Lord has led the Cumans, Philistines [sic], and schismatic Slavs to the same [faith], who now rejoice in the grace of Christ. Indeed, they are even ashamed of their former perverse state (Fig. 6).⁹³

▲ Fig. 6. Drawing of MS Basel, Öffentliche Bibliothek der Universität Basel, A VI 15, fol. 94r (detail).

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Omnia tempus habent, et temporibus suis concta moventur sub sole:

Bartholomew's Circular Letter and King Tomaš's Mass Baptism Campaign

The parallels between Bartholomew's justifications and the methods employed by King Tomaš suggest more than mere coincidence; this section considers how the letter might have influenced the royal court as well as the Franciscans, and how it remained accessible to those tasked with implementing the king's policy. The writings preserved in the Basel manuscript are clearly centred on the affairs of the Orthodox Slavs and Vlachs, as well as the policies of the Hungarian king. Their ideological underpinnings can be seen as reflected, for example, in a charter targeting certain Slavs and Vlachs issued in Timișoara (16 January 1400), or in the anti-Orthodox activities of the prominent Observant Franciscans James of the Marches (1436) and John of Capistrano (1455/56) in Transylvania.⁹⁴ In a letter dated 6 January 1456, John of Capistrano urged the lords of Transylvania to act against the Orthodox and Hussites within their domains, citing the example of John Hunyadi, who had already burned their churches (described as 'synagogues of Satan') and compelled the 'schismatic' priests either to accept baptism in the Roman rite or face expulsion.⁹⁵ An undated papal letter (likely from early 1456) to the legate Juan Carvajal reports a complaint made by the 'Greeks' that 'Brother John of Capistrano rebaptises, burns churches, devastates images — which, as they say, are consigned to the flames, something even the Turks do not do'.⁹⁶

Although Bartholomew's letter refers to Bosnia only sporadically, it should not be overlooked as an area of potential application. It offers a comprehensive and effective guide on how to conduct a campaign of mass baptism under coercion and how to enlist the support and cooperation of the nobility—precisely what the friars in Bosnia required in 1459. Moreover, James of the Marches and John of Capistrano maintained contacts with the Bosnian vicariate during the mid-1400s, and the fact that the latter called for rebaptisms under compulsion on his own initiative, without the authorisation of the pope or his representatives, warrants further investigation into the ideas circulating within the Franciscan Observant milieu.

On 21 December 1435, at an assembly in Székesfehérvár, James of the Marches, vicar of Bosnia, was reported to have lamented over the situation in Bosnia in the following way:

He exposed many things about the king of Bosnia, who arrived to us at Székesfehérvár that day, saying, that this king was a fake Christian, that he was not baptised in truth, and indeed he was prohibiting to baptise his subjects by the Friars Minor who are in his kingdom; as

in that kingdom there are adherents of the sect of the Manichaeans; and that had the emperor commanded the king so that the people of the kingdom of Bosnia should be baptised, then within six months that entire population would be baptised.⁹⁷

What the king of Bosnia, Tvrtko II, was prohibiting must have been, in essence, the very measures described by Bartholomew—measures that could potentially destabilise the kingdom—rather than the voluntary baptisms of those who had willingly sought conversion, which had been taking place in Bosnia since the establishment of the vicariate. The six-month mass baptism campaign that James envisioned appears as similar to what happened eventually in 1459, as much as it is reflective of the attitude presented by Bartholomew in his letter. It is possible that James, as vicar of Bosnia from mid-1435, was inspired by the recollections of Louis I's campaigns, if not directly by Bartholomew's circular letter itself, which he may have encountered in one of the convents. What James lacked, however, was the support of the Bosnian king for such an undertaking. He sought to remedy this by appealing to the influence of Sigismund of Luxembourg. Under imperial pressure, Tvrtko II issued a charter on 25 January 1436, allowing the Observant Franciscans to preach and baptise within his realm and pledging not to obstruct their efforts.⁹⁸ However, James abandoned his ambitions in Bosnia and redirected his focus towards the persecution of the Hussites in south-eastern Hungary, where he acted as an inquisitor.⁹⁹ The *Krstjani* were unaffected this time, but circumstances in Bosnia began to change too.

The appointment of the bishop of Hvar, Tommaso Tommasini, as papal legate to Bosnia on 12 September 1439—shortly after the union with the Orthodox Church at the Council of Florence—alongside the accession of Stjepan Tomaš to the throne in late 1443, marked the beginning of a very close relationship between the Holy See and the Bosnian kingdom.¹⁰⁰ Tomaš, in addition to facing increasing pressure from the Ottomans, was confronted with a number of internal challenges. As the illegitimate son of King Ostoja, and already married to a commoner, he struggled to secure recognition. The Grand Voivode of Bosnia, Stjepan Kosača, refused to acknowledge his rule, plunging the kingdom into civil war. From an early stage, the Roman curia offered Tomaš support in legitimising his rule and securing the backing of Latin Christian powers, in return for his conversion and a promise to expel heretics from the realm, as evidenced by two papal bulls issued on 29 May 1445.¹⁰¹ This rapprochement was followed by the foundation of Franciscan convents in Bosnia, and several Bosnian noble families establishing contact with the curia on their own, seeking papal patronage.¹⁰²

Despite the rapid growth of Catholic influence in Bosnia, the *Krstjani* do not appear to have been persecuted until 1459.¹⁰³ This sparked tensions with the Franciscans. A papal letter dated 11 November 1445, addressed to Tommasini, reports that they had excommunicated King Tomaš for not only tolerating the 'Manichaeans', but also for showing honour to their 'elected'. The papal legate was instructed to investigate the matter, and if he found the king's claims regarding the political strength of the 'Manichaeans' to be true—and if the honour shown to their leaders constituted 'merely human respect, not worship, from which no insult to God would follow' (a justification echoed in the *Dubia Ecclesiastica*)—he was

to compel the friars to resume administering the sacraments to Tomaš.¹⁰⁴ The outcome of Tommasini's inquiry is unknown, but by 18 June 1447 the king had been allowed to retain two Franciscans as his chaplains.¹⁰⁵ Throughout his reign, Tomaš continued to support the friars of the Bosnian vicariate, suggesting that the dispute had been resolved through Tommasini's mediation and that the Franciscans maintained a significant role in both the religious and political life of the royal court.

Not all nobles supported the kingdom's new Catholic policy. A papal letter to Tommasini, dated 1 February 1448, records that the legate had personally informed the curia that, in addition to the religiosi (*Krstjani*), certain noblemen and barons—including Stjepan Kosača and Ivaniš Pavlović—continued to persist in heresy.¹⁰⁶ Kosača's position was particularly significant, as his domain encompassed the southern half of the kingdom, and for much of the time he remained openly hostile to King Tomaš. Kosača tolerated the *Krstjani*, among whom *Gost Radin* rose to considerable prominence in his service as an advisor and diplomat.¹⁰⁷ He also supported the Orthodox Church through new foundations, and in 1448 he adopted the title 'Duke of St Sava' in honour of the Serbian saint, whose relics were kept in Mileševa, then under his control. This did not prevent him, however, from presenting himself as a Catholic to the Roman curia—though in time, it grew disillusioned with him.¹⁰⁸

Ottoman pressure on Bosnia continued steadily throughout King Tomaš's reign, while prospects for assistance from the Latin Christian powers remained bleak. The king negotiated a treaty with the widow of the Serbian despot, arranging the marriage of his son, Stjepan Tomašević, to the despot's daughter. Tomašević was granted the title of despot and arrived in Smederevo in March 1459. The Ottomans, displeased by the Bosnian dynasty's eastward expansion, marched on Smederevo, which surrendered on 20 June 1459. At the Council of Mantua, held at the same time, Hungarian envoys blamed the Bosnian king for having surrendered the stronghold to the Turks and thereby betraying the Christian cause. This represented a significant setback for Tomaš, a neophyte whose faith had remained uncontested until that point at the curia, and whose hopes largely rested on the support from it.¹⁰⁹ In such dire circumstances, Tomaš decided to take action against the heretics in order to appease the pope. *Commentaries* by Pius II report that in the following way:

The King of Bosnia to atone for having surrendered Smederevo to the Turks and to give proof to his religious faith (or, as many thought, to cloak his avarice), forced the Manichaeans, who were very numerous in his kingdom, to be baptised or to emigrate leaving their property behind them. About 12,000 were baptised, forty, or a few more, persisted in their heresy, and fled to their comrade in perfidy, Stjepan, duke of Bosnia, three of the leaders of this heresy, men prominent at court, were sent in chains to the pope by the bishop of Nin.¹¹⁰

On 14 May 1461, in a public ceremony held at St Peter's, the three individuals—Juraj Kučinić, Stojsav Tvrtković, and Radmil Vučinić—formally renounced heresy by accepting fifty articles of the Catholic faith, set in opposition to fifty 'Manichean errors' as compiled by Cardinal Juan Torquemada.¹¹¹ Subsequently, on 2 August 1461, they were taken under papal protection and granted permission to build churches on their estates in Bosnia.¹¹² Two of the men remained within the Catholic Church, while the third eventually fled to Duke Stjepan.¹¹³ A Venetian charter dated 10

March 1466 allowed *Gost Radin* to enter Venetian territory 'with fifty or sixty persons of his rule and sect'.¹¹⁴ Earlier that year, Radin had also left his testament in Dubrovnik, which remains a significant source for the study of the Bosnian Church.¹¹⁵ Beyond this, evidence concerning the *Krstjani* is both scarce and ambiguous.

The decision to begin the repression of the *Krstjani* must have been a difficult one for King Tomaš. Whatever his personal views, they had been part of Bosnian religious life for longer than the Franciscans, had taken deep root in society, and maintained close ties with the noble families. Whenever urged to act against heresy, Bosnian rulers consistently offered excuses, citing the potentially catastrophic political consequences of such actions.¹¹⁶ They tended to placate papal envoys with promises rather than concrete measures. As late as May 1456, the papal envoy Nicholas Barbucci reported that Tomaš had declined to engage in any anti-Ottoman activity, citing fears over the influence and numbers of the 'Manichaeans'.¹¹⁷ It seems that launching a large-scale campaign of baptisms targeting previously unwilling segments of the population placed considerable strain on royal authority. The effort required Tomaš to mobilise and maintain control over the state apparatus throughout the process, effectively subjecting his power to a significant stress test. The conflated account in the *Commentaries* may give the impression that Tomaš's campaign proceeded smoothly; however, a papal bull dated 28 December 1460, recently published by Špoljarić, indicates that there were still individuals 'rising against the Catholic faith' at the time.¹¹⁸

After accusations of collaboration with the Turks were levelled against King Tomaš, it is likely that the royal court sought the counsel of the Franciscans on how best to appease the pope—who, notably, appears not to have been consulted beforehand.¹¹⁹ Furthermore, there was no papal legate in Bosnia at that time.¹²⁰ As the only group capable of organising and executing a campaign of mass baptism, the Franciscans would have been required to present a practical and coherent plan for its implementation, ensuring it would not be undermined by moral, legal, or practical ambiguities. Although issued nearly a century earlier and originally addressing the policies of Louis I, Bartholomew's circular letter appears to have remained relevant to the Bosnian context. It may therefore have served as a valuable reference for the Franciscans in facilitating the campaign. Firstly, the letter could have been used to legitimise—or at least frame—the campaign within the parameters of 'conditional' rather than 'absolute' violence. Bartholomew wrote:

But against this reasoning, some object that coerced services are not pleasing to God [...]. To this I answer that violence is twofold, some is absolute while other conditional. Absolute violence is, for example, in a case when a Jew or a Saracen is captured by a Christian, and bonded, not agreeing but struggling, is violently baptised. Such an individual does not receive the sacrament nor the sacrament's essence. Therefore, it is not baptism, nor is such a service pleasing to God, not for those receiving it nor for those administering it. All arguments and authoritative statements of the masters asserting that no one should be baptised through violence can be interpreted in this way. On the other hand, conditional violence is when a condition is presented to someone, such as, 'if you do not wish to accept my faith and baptism, then leave my kingdom or pay a certain amount; or I will have you beheaded'. Under such compulsion, a person may change his mind, making a

virtue of necessity, choosing baptism freely, desiring to escape harm, and saying, 'I want this; I receive it with all my heart'. Such a person, even if baptised insincerely, does indeed receive the sacrament, though not the sacrament's essence, which is Christ's grace. However, by living among Christians, he will soon come to consent to the faith and take delight in the reception of the sacraments. In this way, not only schismatics—about whom there is no doubt—but even Saracens and pagans may be compelled. In this way, the Hungarians and Germans were converted, as it is said. Even if their service is not pleasing to God in the beginning, it pleases Him later; but at the very least, the service of those who enforce it is always pleasing.¹²¹

The letter could also have been used by the friars as a practical resource to persuade the Bosnian nobility to comply with and support the campaign. Although many nobles were already Catholic, this did not necessarily mean they would favour such a campaign. Bartholomew had written his letter precisely to counteract negligence and resistance to similar measures among the Hungarian nobility, and there is no reason to believe that the Bosnians would have been any more receptive. The letter went to great lengths to demonstrate the spiritual and social benefits of the campaign. It emphasised that salvation was not possible outside the Church, and mass baptism did not constitute a sacrilegious abuse of the sacrament, that not all those baptised would need to be coerced, and that even the unwilling—or at least their children—might eventually come to accept the faith. Bartholomew further clarified that those to be baptised required no prior probation, and the fact that some Slavs and Vlachs claimed to have already been baptised was not, in his view, a valid objection.

Bartholomew argued that the measures discussed were not motivated by an 'ends justify the means' rationale. Rather, it entailed nothing contrary to the laws of God and the Church, and he mentioned the papal bull *Devotionis sinceritas* in support. He explained that even if such measures had not been undertaken previously, this was mainly because no king before Louis had been presented with the opportunity to carry out such a 'holy work', citing the scripture: 'to everything there is a season, and a time to every purpose under the sun' (Eccl. 3:1). Finally, matters of faith were not to be left solely to prelates and members of the clergy exercising spiritual authority. Secular lords, too, were called upon to play their part in eradicating schism and heresy as servants of God, and those who remained negligent were to be removed from office. The fact that the letter was written after Louis's major conversion campaigns suggests that Bartholomew not only anticipated such objections to arise but drew on his own experience to clarify ambiguities and counter arguments of nobles or ecclesiastics. Most, if not all, of these points would likely have been seen by the Friars Minor as a valuable set of pre-formulated polemical arguments—reinforced with scriptural references and appeals to ecclesiastical authors—directly applicable to the Bosnian situation, where king's orders needed to be enforced (Fig. 7).¹²²

Although nearly a century separates the issuing of Bartholomew's letter and Tomaš's repressions, the text appears

to have been preserved within the Bosnian vicariate in the fifteenth century. The papal bull *Devotionis sinceritas* was among the documents examined by Čremošnik in Ljubljana, where a corpus of the Bosnian vicariate's sources has been preserved, likely taken away further into the Christian lands due to the Ottoman threat.¹²³ The Basel manuscript, which preserves three of Bartholomew's writings along with other polemics against the Orthodox Church, originates from the local Dominican convent. It was compiled by Ivan Stojković (also known as John of Ragusa), a Dominican friar from Dubrovnik and a prominent theologian at the Council of Basel.¹²⁴ In May 1435, he was appointed the council's envoy to Constantinople to negotiate a union with the Eastern Church.¹²⁵ He spent two years in the imperial capital before returning to Basel, where he died in 1443, leaving behind a significant collection of manuscripts. Church union was undoubtedly a matter of great importance to Stojković, and he would therefore have taken an active interest in Latin writings on the subject, including polemical works such as those by Bartholomew of La Verna. It is likely he acquired them from his native Dubrovnik, with which he remained in contact throughout his career. At the time, the Bosnian vicariate maintained four convents within Ragusan territory, with an archive located in Ston.¹²⁶ If Stojković obtained Bartholomew's writings from there in the 1430s, this would suggest that the texts were circulating among the vicariate's convents and would have been accessible to the Bosnian Franciscans by 1459.

Conclusions

The circular letter issued by Bartholomew of La Verna, offering his commentary on the bull *Devotionis sinceritas*, provides valuable insight into the ideological underpinnings and socio-political atmosphere surrounding the mass baptism campaign undertaken by King Tomaš in Bosnia in 1459. This paper has argued that the campaign likely unfolded within a conceptual framework shaped, at least in part, by Bartholomew's letter. Originally composed nearly a century earlier in connection with the conversion campaigns of Louis I, the letter articulated a rationale for coercive religious policy, distinguishing between different forms of violence and advocating for state-supported efforts to bring wayward populations into the Catholic fold. Bartholomew's arguments—rooted in scripture, canon law, and patristic and scholastic authorities—may have significantly informed the planning and justification of the 1459 baptisms. They offered a ready-made set of polemical responses to both moral and practical objections, serving to reassure the friars involved and to persuade reluctant members of the nobility. Such justification was crucial, given the extent to which the campaign stretched the resources and authority of the Bosnian political apparatus. The legacy of Bartholomew's pastoral and polemical vision thus played a subtle yet influential role in the final chapter of the medieval Bosnian Church's history.

▼ Fig. 7. Drawing of ms Basel, Öffentliche Bibliothek der Universität Basel, A VI 15, fol. 94v (detail).

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Istam in die xpi: Stephanus p. dubius fide in fidelitate nri omni
mededi qui fide vitat ignorat. Leo pp. Qui alios q no pot ab er
nore no rhorat pspny errore demonstrat illud de fide cathoim

ADDENDUM

The text is based on the edition of the letter published by Lasić, maintaining his abbreviation interpretations and most of his editorial interpolations indicated in square brackets. However, his classicising emendations

have been removed to reflect the original spelling of the manuscript. Some of his substitutions were reverted to the original words. Lasić, 'Fr. Bartholomaei de Alverna scripta', pp. 68–81; UB Basel, A VI 15, 91r–94v.

LATIN TEXT

EPISTULA FRATRIBUS VICARIE BOSNE

In Christo sibi karissimis fratribus Vicarie Bosne frater Bartholomaeus de Alverna, eorum vicarius licet indignus, salutem et pacem in Domino sempiternam.

Quia Ecclesia [procurat] sacrae fidei propagationem et animarum salutem, [circa quam] tam vestra quam mea favente Deo principalis versatur intentio, ac erga extirpationem errorum et conversionem schismaticorum, inter quas a Christo destinati pro earum salute conversamur iuxta nostrae professionis evangelicam regulam; non solum verbis et exemplis sed etiam aliis modis congruentibus insudare debemus, et ubi expediens fuerit, principes et dominos alios ad hoc perficiendum inducere, secundum quod iura clamant; quod dominus Papa, scilicet Urbanus VI, in sua bulla nuper nobis missa declaravit.

Idcirco propter quosdam simplices et negli[g]entes ac detractores et depravatores huius sancti operis nuper incep[t]i per illustrissimum dominum regem Hungarorum ad vestram incitationem scilicet de conversione et baptismo istorum Sclavorum et Vlachorum existentium in suo regno, decrevi ad maiorem declarationem nostrae intentionis et rescissionem dubiorum circa hanc materiam quasdam rationes seu motiva breviter iungere, quae nos inducere habent ad huiusmodi negotii executionem etiam per principes procurandam. Quattuor autem sunt principaliter inductiva, scilicet ratio, natura, Scriptura et exemplum.

I – Primum inductivum: ratio

Circa primum nota VII principales rationes cum VII annexis dubiis declaratis. Prima ratio sumitur ex parte divini obsequii, ad quod omnis creatura obligatur. Cum enim nullum obsequium nullumque sacrificium possit esse Deo gratius quam animarum salutem procurare, quae tanti sunt pretii, ut totus visibilis mundus pro una anima commutari non possit; tantae aestimationis, quod Deum [induxerit], ut Filium suum unigenitum daret ad mortem pro earum redemptione. Ergo nihil carius dare possumus Christo redemptori quam animas, quas tam care redemit.

Sed contra hanc rationem obiciunt quidam, quod Deo non placent coacta servicia, quia nullum dicitur opus meritorium, nec voluntarium. Ad hoc respondeo, quod duplex est violentia: quaedam absoluta, quaedam condicionalis. [Violentia absoluta est], verbi gratia, in proposito: Aliquis Iudaeus vel Saracenus a christianis capitur, ligatur et non consentiens, sed renitens et contradicens baptizatus violenter. Talis nec recipit sacramentum nec rem sacramenti. Ideo nec est baptismus, nec tale obsequium Deo placet, non solum suscipientium, sed neque facientium. Et de hac violentia exponi possunt omnes rationes et auctoritates magistrorum dicentium, quod nullus violenter debet baptizari. Alio modo dicitur

ENGLISH TRANSLATION

LETTER TO THE FRIARS OF THE VICARIATE OF BOSNIA (translation)

To the brothers of the Vicariate of Bosnia, most beloved in Christ, Brother Bartholomew of La Verna, their, though unworthy, vicar, sends greetings and eternal peace in the Lord.

Since the Church endeavours to promote the holy faith and the salvation of souls, about which both your concern and mine, with God's favour, are chiefly occupied, and because for the eradication of errors and the conversion of schismatics—among whom we, appointed by Christ for their salvation, labour according to the evangelical rule of our profession—not only by words and examples but also by other suitable means we must diligently strive, and, wherever it is expedient, induce princes and other lords to bring this to completion, as the laws prescribe, which our lord pope, namely Urban VI, has recently declared to us in his bull.

Therefore, on account of certain simple and negligent persons, as well as detractors and corrupters of this holy work recently undertaken by the most illustrious lord king of the Hungarians—namely, to your encouragement, concerning the conversion and baptism of those Slavs and Vlachs residing in his kingdom—I have resolved, for a fuller declaration of our intention and the removal of doubts about this matter, to briefly set down certain reasons or motives, which ought to move us to procure the execution of such a work even through the agency of princes. There are principally four inducements: namely, reason, nature, scripture, and example.

I – The First Inducement: Reason

Concerning the first, note seven principal reasons along with seven related questions that are explained. The first reason is taken from the perspective of divine service, to which every creature is bound. For no service or sacrifice can be more pleasing to God than to procure the salvation of souls, which are of such great worth that the entire visible world could not be exchanged for a single soul; and of such high estimation that it moved God to give his only begotten Son to death for their redemption. Therefore, we can offer nothing dearer to Christ the Redeemer than souls, whom he redeemed at such a great cost.

But against this reasoning, some object that coerced services are not pleasing to God, since no work is called meritorious unless it is voluntary. To this I answer that violence is twofold, some is absolute while other conditional. Absolute violence is, for example, in a case when a Jew or a Saracen is captured by a Christian, and bonded, not agreeing but struggling, is violently baptised. Such an individual does not receive the sacrament nor the sacrament's essence. Therefore, it is not baptism, nor is such a service pleasing to God, not for those receiving it nor for those administering it. All arguments and authoritative statements of the masters asserting that no one should be baptised through violence can be interpreted in this way. On the other hand, conditional violence

violentia condicionalis, verbi gratia, et cum alicui proponitur talis condicio: Si non vis recipere meam fidem et baptismum, ex eas regnum meum vel solvas tantum; et quod plus est, te decapitabo. Talis etiam, sic coactus, mutat voluntatem; de necessitate facit virtutem; eligit sponte baptizari, cupiens liberari a malo; dicit: Volo, toto corde recipio. Talis, etsi fecte baptizatur; licet non recipiat rem sacramenti, scilicet Christi gratiam, sed tamen sacramentum recipit, et cum christianis vivens in brevi consentiet fidei et delectabitur in sacramentorum [receptione]. Isto modo non solum schismatici, de quibus non dubium est, sed etiam Sarraceni et gentiles compelli possunt. Isto modo Hungari et Alamani conversi sunt, ut dicitur. Etsi non placet Deo eorum servitium pro modo, placet postea; sed saltem obsequium facientium semper placet.

Secunda ratio sumitur ex parte debiti amoris Christi. Constat enim ex divino precepto, quod homo quilibet tenetur diligere proximum sicut se ipsum. Cum igitur unusquisque debet se diligere recto ordine dilectionis, - et ibi est ordo rectissimus, ut se ipsum diligat ad illud bonum, ad quod creatus [est] - illo ordine et suum proximum diligere tenetur. Unde inquit Christus: 'Hoc est praeceptum meum, ut diligatis etc. sicut dilexi vos' [Joan. 15.12]. Augustinus ad hoc: 'Amate, ad quod amavi vos'.¹²⁷ Ergo quilibet conari debet modis et viis, quibus potest, ut proximus salvetur. 'Quia maiorem caritatem nemo habet' etc.

Contra hoc dici potest, quod ille non est amor rectus nec ordinatus, nec est eis procurare salutem, sed maiorem damnationem, ex quo coacti suscipunt, non gratiam iustum facientem, sed sacramentum ecclesiasticum.

Ad hoc respondeo, quod non omnes coacti [sunt]. Immo pro maiori parte cum sua simplicitate gaudenter suscipiunt dicentes: Ex quo Deo et dominis nostris placet, ut simus sub una fide, et nobis placere debet. Immo multotiens, ut probavimus, gaudendo ad baptismum venerunt, etiam pressuram facientes. Et si aliqui modo coguntur, postea gaudent et gratias agunt de tali coactione. Etsi omnes gratiam non recipiunt, aliqui tamen recipiunt. Nec enim omnes christiani sacramentum digne recipiunt. Utinam, de quo dolens dico, tertia pars nostrorum christianorum semper susciperent in sacramentis gratiam. Quibus tamen sacramenta salutem necessitatis tempore [praestantia] negare non possumus, quia ministri sumus sacramentorum, rerum signa dare possumus, gratiam dare non possumus. Unde dico, quod istis non maiorem damnationem, cum sint extra gremium salutis, procuramus, sed salutem, involventes eos ecclesiasticis sacramentis, quibus carent et sine quibus salvari nequeunt. Etsi non omnes salvantur, tamen una pars salvabitur, quae ex toto perierat; et saltem filii et nepotes erunt boni christiani.

Tertia ratio, ex parte mali evitandi. Quia nullus absque gravi peccato et periculo animae suae equanimiter ferre potest tantarum animarum perditionem; vel potest occurrere et non vult, sed tacet et dissimulat et quasi eis consentire videtur; ex quo iuxta Apostolum Rom. primo simul cum eis facit se dignum eterna morte. Insuper, dicti schismatici non solum ipsi pereunt, sed etiam nostros christianos, cum quibus conversantur et matrimonia contrahunt, ducunt ad perditionem. Quare innumeri, ut nobis constat, negantes catholicam fidem, facti sunt schismatici et ab eis rebaptizati. Unde non solum ad fidem veram cogendi sunt, sed nolentes et protervi, tamquam membra putrida et oves morbidae et infectae de medio tollendae. Unde Christus: 'Si oculus tuus scandalizaverit te' etc. [Matth. 18, 9], quod mystice, ut ait Hieronymus de

is when a condition is presented to someone, such as: 'If you do not wish to accept my faith and baptism, then leave my kingdom or pay a certain amount; or I will have you beheaded'. Under such compulsion, a person may change his mind, making a virtue of necessity, choosing baptism freely, desiring to escape harm, and saying, 'I want this; I receive it with all my heart'. Such a person, even if baptised insincerely, does indeed receive the sacrament, though not the sacrament's essence, which is Christ's grace. However, by living among Christians, he will soon come to consent to the faith and take delight in the reception of the sacraments. In this way, not only schismatics—about whom there is no doubt—but even Saracens and pagans may be compelled. In this way, the Hungarians and Germans were converted, as it is said. Even if their service is not pleasing to God in the beginning, it pleases Him later; but at the very least, the service of those who enforce it is always pleasing.

The second reason is taken from the perspective of the obligation of love owed to Christ. For it is established by divine precept that every person is bound to love his neighbour as himself. Since, therefore, each person ought to love himself in the right order of charity—and that order is most correct, that he loves himself for that good for which he was created—in that same order he is bound to love his neighbour. Hence Christ says: 'This is my commandment, that you love one another as I have loved you' (John 15:12). Augustine on this: 'Love, to the end that I have loved you'.¹²⁷ Therefore, everyone ought to strive in whatever ways he can that his neighbour may be saved. 'For no one has greater love [than the one who lays down his life for his friends]' (John 15:13).

Against this it can be said that such love is neither upright nor rightly ordered, nor is it to procure salvation for them, but rather greater damnation, since, being coerced, they receive not the grace that makes righteous, but only the ecclesiastical sacrament.

I reply, in short, that not all are compelled. Indeed, for the most part, they accept it gladly in their simplicity, saying: 'Since it pleases God and our lords that we should be under one faith, it ought to please us as well'. In fact, as we have often found, they have come to baptism with joy, even pressing forward eagerly. And if some are indeed compelled at first, afterward they rejoice and give thanks for such compulsion. Although not all receive grace, yet some do receive it. In fact, not all Christians receive the sacrament worthily. Would that, though I say this with sorrow, even a third part of our Christians would always receive grace in the sacraments. Nevertheless, we cannot deny the sacraments to them at a time of necessity for salvation, because we are ministers of the sacraments: we can give the outward signs, but we cannot give grace. Therefore, I say that, by this, we do not bring greater damnation upon them, since they are outside the fold of salvation, but rather salvation, by involving them in the sacraments of the Church, which they lack and without which they cannot be saved. Even though not all will be saved, still a part will be saved who would otherwise have been utterly lost—and at the very least, their children and grandchildren will be good Christians.

The third reason is on the part of avoiding evil. Because no one, without committing grave sin and endangering his own soul, can calmly endure the loss of so many souls; or can help and refuses, but remains silent and dissimulates, he seems as though to consent with them — and thus, according to the Apostle in Romans 1, he makes himself, together with them, worthy of eternal death. Moreover, those schismatics not only perish themselves, but also lead our own Christians, since they associate with them and contract marriages with them, into perdition. For which reason countless people, as we know for certain, denying the Catholic faith, have become schismatics and have been rebaptized by them. Therefore, they must not only be compelled to the true faith, but the unwilling and the obstinate must be removed—like putrid limbs and diseased, infected sheep—from the midst. Thus, Christ says: 'If your eye scandalizes you, pluck it out [and throw it away]' (Matthew 18:9), which, as Jerome says, must be understood in a mystical sense

perfidis abscindendis, qui scandalum sunt corpori Ecclesie, intelligi debet. Ergo omnibus modis cogi debent pro earum salute, vel expellendi sunt tales protervi, ut puta eorum falsi sacerdotes et pseudo religiosi, ne alios inficiant.

Sed obicitur contra hanc rationem, quod primo instrui deberent de fide et moribus Ecclesie, et postea baptizari, demum provideri eis de sacerdotibus et curatis idoneis; alias non evitatur periculum, sed maius scandalum oritur. Sic nec istam fidem servant et primam negaverunt.

Ad quod dicendum, quod quantum ad fundamentum fidei et illa, quae necessaria sunt ad salutem, aequae bene sunt instructi ab antiquo sicut nostri christiani simplices. Sufficit enim eis fides implicita cum confessione beatae Trinitatis. Non enim sunt sicut Iudaei vel pagani, sed christiani a nobis divisi, et oves errantes, quae non solum vocibus sed flagellis ad ovile veri pastoris reduci habent; nec expectandum est, ut isti simplices instruantur in divinis scripturis, quia isto modo numquam aliquis Ebreorum converteretur, nec mores Ecclesie addiscere potuit, nisi ii scholas compellantur intrare, nec audire possunt merita salutis.

Quod obicitur de sacerdotibus et prima eorum fide, dico, quod si illi eorum sacerdotes essent rite ordinati, et in illa eorum secta esset aliqua spes salutis, recte obiceretur. Sed, cum sint falsi et deceptores, et iam propter suam rusticitatem perdidit omnem ritum ecclesiasticum et formas sacramentorum, maxime inter istos Sclavos et Vlachos, ut dicitur infra, et populus ille in hac secta salvari non possit, maxime qui credunt suam sectam meliorem nostra. Nec Ecclesia baptizati [sunt]. They have not been baptized in the Church; and even if they had been, or are pretended to have been, they would still believe themselves to be baptized. Ex quo extra Ecclesie unitatem morantur, salvari non possunt, potissime adulti cum calugis Ecclesiam blasphemantes. Nulla ergo ratione dimittendi sunt in sua misera secta. Et si tam cito sufficientes curatos habere non possunt, paulatim procurabunt habere, quando primi expellentur. Nec enim Hungaria habuit qui in principio suae conversionis xx millia clericorum et religiosorum, qui favente [Deo] in ea modo sunt; licet, quantum ad hoc, multum debet inculpari negligentia et avaritia dominorum et prelatorum regni, ad quos pertinet providere, et nihil curant.

Quarta ratio accipitur ex parte spiritualis fructus et temporalis commodi. Quis enim aestimare potest tantum fructum spiritualem? Nam si iuxta Christi verbum: 'Gaudium est in caelo super uno peccatore' etc. [Luc. 15.7], quanto magis debet mille milibus iam conversis et eorum posteris usque ad finem mundi? Gaudium et matris Ecclesie filiis aggregatis. Gaudium et istius primae videre omnes in unitate fidei insimul commorantes. Est insuper commodum temporale, scilicet maior fortitudo regni in istis confinibus, et maior fidelitas istius gentis erga regem et suos dominos; quia numquam poterunt suis dominis fideles esse, qui per alienam fidem Deo infideles existunt. Multa etiam mala, scilicet latrocinia et homicidia occulta, cessabunt, quae modo sine conscientia una cum externis de sua lingua et secta contra Christianos faciunt. Erga laborandum est pro predictis bonis utilitatibus et remedio malorum.

Contra hanc rationem dicunt quidam: Non sunt facienda mala, ut eveniant bona.¹²⁸ Nam pro totius mundi conversione debet quis peccare vel aliquid facere contra Deum et sanctae Ecclesie determinationem.

Ad hoc dicendum, quod in isto opere nullam malum

about cutting off the faithless who are a scandal to the body of the Church. Therefore, by every means, they must be compelled for the sake of their salvation—or, in the case of such obstinate people, expelled, for example their false priests and pseudo-monks, so that they do not infect others.

But it is objected to this reasoning that, first, they ought to be instructed about the faith and the morals of the Church, and afterward be baptized, and finally be provided with suitable priests and pastors; otherwise, the danger is not avoided, but greater scandal arises. In this way, neither do they keep this faith, and they have denied the former one.

To this it must be replied that, as regards the foundation of the faith and those things necessary for salvation, they have been instructed just as well since ancient times as our own simple Christians. For it is sufficient for them to have implicit faith along with confession of the Blessed Trinity. For they are not like Jews or pagans, but Christians separated from us, the wandering sheep, who must be brought back to the fold of the true shepherd not only by voices but also by whips. Nor should we wait for these simple people to be instructed in the divine Scriptures, because in this way no Hebrew would ever be converted, nor could they learn the morals of the Church unless they were compelled to attend schools, nor can they hear the doctrines of salvation.

As for the objection concerning their priests and their original faith, I say that if their priests had been duly ordained, and if there were any hope of salvation in their sect, the objection would be valid. But since they are false and deceivers, and by their own rusticity have already lost all ecclesiastical rite and the forms of the sacraments—especially among these Slavs and Vlachs, as will be said below—and since that people cannot be saved within this sect, above all those who believe their sect is better than ours; et adhuc essent, vel finguntur, baptizatos se [esse] crederent. Since they remain outside the unity of the Church, they cannot be saved, especially the adults who blaspheme the Church together with the calogers. Therefore, by no reasoning should they be left in their wretched sect. And if they cannot so quickly have sufficient pastors, they will gradually arrange to have them when the first ones are expelled. For Hungary at the beginning of its conversion did not have anyone who could maintain twenty thousand clerics and religious, who by God's favour are there now. Although, in this regard, the negligence and avarice of the lords and prelates of the kingdom—whose duty it is to provide for these things but who care nothing—must be greatly reproved.

The fourth reason is taken from the aspect of spiritual benefit and temporal advantage. For who could estimate such a great spiritual benefit? For if, according to the word of Christ, "There is joy in heaven over one sinner" (Luke 15:7), how much more over a thousand thousands now converted, and over their descendants until the end of the world? There is joy also for the Holy Mother Church, to see her children added to her. Joy likewise to see all these formerly separated people dwelling together in the unity of the faith. Moreover, there is a temporal advantage, namely, greater strength for the kingdom in these border areas, and greater loyalty of this nation toward the king and their lords; for they can never be faithful to their earthly lords when, through an alien faith, they are unfaithful to God. Many evils will also cease—such as thefts and hidden murders—which they now commit without scruple together with outsiders of their own language and sect against Christians. Therefore, efforts must be made for these aforesaid good advantages and the remedying of these evils.

Against this reasoning some say: 'Evil things must not be done so that good things may come forth.'¹²⁸ For even for the conversion of the whole world, no one ought to sin or do anything against God and the determination of the Holy Church.

To this it must be replied that in this work no evil nor anything of the nature of evil can be proved. Nothing is done against God's commandments, nor against love of neighbour, nor to one's own dis-

nec aliquid de genere mali ostendi potest. Nil agitur contra Dei precepta, nec contra proximi dilectionem aut sui deformationem. Immo, econtra, totum fit pro Dei honore et proximi salute, ut dictum [est]. Et quod non sit contra decretum Ecclesie, patet per bullam domini Papae, et infra clarius dicitur.

Quinta ratio accipitur ex professione catholice fidei. Ut enim patet ex illo articulo Symboli: 'Credo unam sanctam Ecclesiam', constat, quod nullus extra Ecclesie unitatem salvari potest. Sic sacra concilia saepe damnaverunt omnem haereticum et schismaticum aliter dogmatizantem, quam sacrosancta Ecclesia diffinivit. Unde dudum Ecclesia Grecos et Bulgros et Rascianos tamquam haereticos damnavit. Hanc sententiam confirmat Augustinus in libro De fide ad Petrum, dicens: 'Frimissime teneet nullatenus dubites omnem, extra Ecclesiam baptizatum, participem fieri non posse aeternae vitae, si ante finem vitae suae huius, catholice non fuerit redditus atque incorporatus Ecclesie'.¹²⁹ Et quia 'si [habeam], inquit Apostolus, omnem fidem et noverim omnia mysteria, caritatem non habeam, nihil sum'. [1 Cor. 13, 2]. Nam et in diebus diluvii neminem extra archam legimus potuisse salvari. 'Frimissime tene, et nullatenus dubites quemlibet haereticum sive schismaticum in nomine Patris et Filii et Spiritus Sancti baptizatum, si Ecclesie catholice non fuerit aggregatus, quantascumque eleemosynas fecerit; etsi pro Christi nomine etiam sanguinem fuderit, nullatenus posse salvari. Omni enim homini, qui Catholice Ecclesie non tenet unitatem, neque baptismus, neque eleemosyna quamlibet copiosa, neque mors pro Christi nomine suscepta, proficere poterit ad salutem, quamdiu in eo haeretica vel schismatica pravitas perseverat, quae ducit ad mortem'.¹³⁰ Ergo omni arte et modo reducendi sunt ad sanctae Ecclesie unitatem, ne pereant.

Item contra hanc rationem fit instantia talis. Cum enim [ante] nos per tanta tempora fuerunt principes et prelati ac religiosi eque boni, immo meliores, et non minoris scientiae, cur illa non fecerunt nec temptaverunt; nisi quia nec reputaverunt necessaria nec utilia?

Ad hoc respondeo, quod multa facta sunt, fiunt et fient, quae ante non fuerunt tam mala quam bona; et multa omittuntur, quae ante erant. Unde dicitur: Nihil novum debet fieri, quod per alios non est factum. Verbum stoliditatis est. Nam aliquando non venerat Christus, non erant Apostoli, nec fuerunt martyres et alii sancti. Non erant tot ordines religiosorum; predicebantur, et postea impleti sunt; et multa erunt, quae non sunt modo. Aliquando non fuerunt Hungari conversi, et modo sunt. Quis iste mirare potest? 'Omnia tempus habent, et temporibus suis cuncta moventur sub sole' [Eccl. 3.1].

Quantum autem ad conversionem istorum, dico, quod ante tempora istius Lodovici regis nullus regum habuerat opportunitatem et potestatem faciendi pro eo, quod in Rascia et Bulgaria fuerunt reges et tyranni potentes, qui non solum predictas terras tenebant in manu forti, immo et ista confinia regni devastabant in tantum, quod quidam rex Rasciae, Stephanus Uroscius, ut audivi ab antiquis, suis hominibus occupavit Machvam, Ussuram et Sirmiam, et omnes ad suum schisma pervertit et iterato baptizavit, ut essent ante catholice [fidei], ut ostendunt vestigia ecclesiarum. Hoc nunc revocamus ad fidem, ex quo illi Christi gratia humiliati sunt. Potius mirandum [est] et dolendum ergo tanta negligere istorum dominorum et prelatorum Hungariae, quod quasi curare videntur de conversione istorum, istos pauperes devorant, expoliant, de eorum salute nil curant. Puto, quod ipsi et partes eorum in die iudicii reddent rationem de omnibus istis.

grace. On the contrary, everything is done for the honour of God and the salvation of one's neighbour, as has been said. And that it is not contrary to the decree of the Church is evident from the bull of our lord the pope, and this will be explained more clearly below.

The fifth reason is taken from the profession of the Catholic faith. For as is evident from that article of the creed: 'I believe in one holy Church', it is clear that no one can be saved outside the unity of the Church. In this way, the sacred councils have often condemned every heretic and schismatic who teaches otherwise than the Holy Church has defined. Thus, long ago, the Church condemned the Greeks, Bulgarians, and Serbians as heretics. This sentence is confirmed by Augustine in the book On the Faith to Peter, saying: 'Hold most firmly, and do not in any way doubt, that everyone baptized outside the Church cannot become a partaker of eternal life, unless before the end of this life he shall have been restored to and incorporated into the Catholic Church'.¹²⁹ And because, as the Apostle says, 'If I have all faith, and know all mysteries, but have no charity, I am nothing'. (1 Cor. 13:2). For also, in the days of the Flood, we read that no one outside the Ark could be saved. 'Hold most firmly, and do not in any way doubt, that any heretic or schismatic baptized in the name of the Father and of the Son and of the Holy Spirit, whatever alms he may have given, and even if for the name of Christ he has shed his blood, can in no way be saved. For to any person who does not hold the unity of the Catholic Church, neither baptism, nor any amount of almsgiving, nor death suffered for the name of Christ can bring salvation, as long as in him there persists the depravity of heresy or schism, which leads to death'.¹³⁰ Therefore, by every means and effort they must be brought back to the unity of the Holy Church, lest they perish.

Likewise, against this reasoning the following objection is raised: Since before our time, for so many generations, there were princes and prelates and religious who were just as good—indeed, even better—and no less learned, why did they neither do these things nor attempt them, unless because they did not consider them necessary or useful?

To this I reply that many things have been done, are done, and will be done, which before did not exist, and are not so much evil as good; and many things are now omitted which formerly were practiced. Thus, it is said: 'Nothing new ought to be done which was not done by others before'. But that is a foolish saying. For once Christ had not yet come, nor were there Apostles, nor had there been martyrs and other saints. There were not so many religious orders; they were foretold and afterward came to fulfilment; and there will be many things which do not exist yet. Once the Hungarians were not converted, and now they are. Who could be surprised at this? 'To everything there is a season, and a time to every purpose under the sun'. (Ecclesiastes 3:1)

As for the conversion of these people, I say that before the time of this King Louis, none of the kings had the opportunity and power to act in this matter. For in Serbia and Bulgaria there were powerful kings and tyrants who not only held those lands with a strong hand but also devastated these bordering regions of the kingdom to such a degree that, as I have heard from the old, a certain king of Serbia, Stephen Uroš, seized Mačva, Usora, and Syrmia with his men, led everyone over to his schism, and rebaptized them, though before they had been of the Catholic faith, as the traces of churches show. This we are now restoring to the faith, since by the grace of Christ they have been humbled. Rather, it is more to be wondered at and lamented that there has been such negligence on the part of the lords and prelates of Hungary, who seem to care so little about the conversion of these people. They devour and despoil these poor souls and care nothing for their salvation. I think that they and their supporters will have to render an account of all these things on the Day of Judgment.

The sixth reason is drawn from the ease of converting these peo-

Sexta ratio ex parte facillimae conversionis huius populi. Quia nec est nec umquam fuit natio, quae sic de facili converteretur sicut isti Sclavi et Vlachi. Non cum gladio, non carcere, non verberibus, sed simplici verbo vel precepto conversi essent etiam omnes. Item perfecti christiani [essent], et nullus remansisset in regno schismaticus, si non impediret neglig[en]tia dominorum et prelatorum, ac avaritia seu potius simonia aliquorum, de quibus taceo. Ergo, ex quo sic faciliter [converti] possunt, quis dicet: Non est laborandum?

Sed contra hanc [rationem] adhuc fortius quidam obiciunt, dicentes: dato, quod converti debeant et compelli ad obedientiam matris Ecclesie, ut dicitis; sed quae ratio [est], ut baptizentur iam baptizati christiani, praesertim cum per doctores non impugnetur forma Grecorum, in qua isti sunt baptizati, vel firmiter credunt se baptizatos, quod sufficit ad salutem. Sufficere deberet, [ut] per manuum impositionem reconciliarentur, sicut fit de Grecis.

Ad hoc dicendum, quod, si formam istam Grecorum servarent, scilicet: ‘Baptizatur servus Christi in nomine’ etc., numquam aliquem baptizarem. Sed pro certo repperimus per multas examinationes et vias, quod isti sacerdotes Sclavorum propter ignorantiam et rusticitatem multam nullam debitam formam et certam servant, et illa quam sciunt non applicat ad materiam. Immo altero anno, quando rex ccccta milia baptizavit inter quadringentos sacerdotes schismaticos non fuerunt inventi, [qui] formam servarent.

Etiam Iohannes, imperator Constantinopolitanus, quando ad regem venit, dixit, audientibus multis: ‘Bene facit rex baptizare istos Sclavos, quia nec Grecam nec Romanam formam secuntur’. Insuper pridie in Ceni¹³¹ coram fratribus nostris dixerunt calugeri, venientes de confinibus Graeciae, contra isto[s] sacerdotes: ‘Isti non sunt sacerdotes, sed canes; nec vere baptizant. Propterea nos eos baptizamus sub conditione, quia non dicitur iteratum, quod ignoratur esse factum’. Dato etiam, quod quidam eorum bene baptizarent, maxime quia noviter calugeri expulsi Atmetis de Graecia per istas partes aliquos docuerunt. Tamen quia pauci sunt, eos distinguere ab aliis non possumus. Et cum etiam hoc esset, magna intricatio in tali examine [esset], nec reputarent se suscipere veram fidem, nec sub conditione baptizarentur. Et omnia fiunt pro bono; nec ex hoc iteramus baptismum, nec abutimur sacramentis, quia non fides sacramentis, sed sacramenta fidei deserviunt. Non dico de sacramento Eucharistiae, quod cum maxima diligentia tractari debet, et non dari non dispositis, quia non est sacramentum necessitatis, sed divinae caritatis.

De eo, quod dicitur: ‘credunt se baptizatos’, non sufficit ad salutem, ex quo, ut dictum est, nobis et eis constat de contrario. Exemplum: Si puer parvus panem venenatum, licet pulchrum, in manu teneat ad mordendum, compellendus est per illos, qui sciunt, illum proicere et bonum suscipere, sicut in proposito notatur.

Septima ratio sumitur ex parte donate potestatis seu dominii. Ad hoc enim tradidit Deus principatus et regna, ut populum subiectum reducant ad cultum unius veri Dei et salvatoris Iesu Christi. Quia, si pro solo pane et mundi gloria dominantur, non erunt maioris meriti, quam ceteri pagani domini. Ergo ipsi tales debent ad fidem catholicam compellere, et ad hoc tenentur de necessitate salutis.

ple. For there is not, nor ever has been, any nation that could be converted so readily as these Slavs and Vlachs. Not by the sword, nor by prison, nor by beatings, but by a simple word or command, all of them would have been converted. Likewise, they would have become perfect Christians, and not a single schismatic would have remained in the kingdom, if it were not for the negligence of the lords and prelates, and the greed—or rather simony—of some, about whom I will remain silent. Therefore, since they can be converted so easily, who can say that no effort should be made?

But against this reasoning some object even more strongly, saying: Granted that they ought to be converted and compelled to obedience to Mother Church, as you claim—but what reason is there that Christians who have already been baptized should be baptized again, especially since the form used by the Greeks, in which these people were baptized, is not rejected by the doctors, or they firmly believe themselves to have been baptized, which is sufficient for salvation? It ought to be enough that they be reconciled by the laying on of hands, as is done with the Greeks.

To this it must be replied that, if they were in fact preserving that Greek form—namely, ‘The servant of Christ is baptized in the name [of the Father, Amen; and of the Son, Amen; and of the Holy Spirit, Amen]’—we would never baptize anyone again. But we have certainly discovered, through many examinations and inquiries, that these priests of the Slavs, because of their great ignorance and rusticity, observe no proper and definite form, and the formula they do know they do not apply to the matter. Indeed, in the other year, when the king baptized four hundred thousand people, among four hundred schismatic priests there were none found who correctly used the form.

Likewise, John, emperor of Constantinople, when he came to the king, said in the hearing of many: ‘The king did the right thing to baptize these Slavs, because they follow neither the Greek nor the Roman rite’. Moreover, just the day before, in Ceni,¹³¹ in the presence of our brethren, the calogers who had come from the confines of Greece said about these priests: ‘These are not priests, but dogs; nor do they truly baptize. Therefore, we baptize them conditionally, because if it is not known if it has been done, it cannot be considered to be repeated’. Even granting that some of them did baptize properly—especially since recently calogers expelled from Mount Athos in Greece have instructed some in these parts—still, because they are few, we are not able to distinguish them from the others. And even if this were the case, there would be great confusion in such an examination, nor would they consider themselves to be receiving the true faith, nor would they be baptized under condition. And everything is done for the sake of the good; nor by this do we repeat baptism or abuse the sacraments, because it is not faith that serves the sacraments, but the sacraments that serve the faith. I am not speaking here of the sacrament of the Eucharist, which must be handled with the greatest care and not given to those unprepared, because it is not a sacrament of necessity, but of divine charity.

As for what is said that ‘they believe themselves to be baptized’, it does not suffice for salvation, since, as has been said, it is clear both to us and to them that the opposite is the case. An example: if a small boy were holding poisoned bread—though it might look fine—in his hand, ready to bite into it, he must be compelled by those who know to throw it away and to receive good bread instead, as is noted in the present case.

The seventh reason is taken from the matter of the power or dominion that has been granted. For God has entrusted principalities and kingdoms precisely so that they may lead the people subject to them back to the worship of the one true God and Saviour, Jesus Christ. For if they exercise dominion only for the sake of bread and the glory of the world, they will have no greater merit than other pagan rulers. Therefore, such rulers must compel their subjects to the Catholic faith, and they are bound to do so out of necessity for their own salvation.

But against this it is objected that secular lords ought not to

Sed contra hoc obicitur, quod domini temporales non debent se impedire de spiritualibus negotiis, sed potius prelati et religiosi verbo et exemplo debent inducere et, si necesse est, spirituali gladio non temporalis rebelles percutere; quia non invenimus apostolos et alios sanctos per tales dominos alios convertisse.

Ad hoc respondeo, quod cum sint Dei ministri ad punitationem malorum et laudem bonorum, ut clare ostendit Apostolus ad Rom. 13: 'Omnis anima' etc. Videre apostoli verba! Et Petrus in epistola: 'subiecti estote' etc. Cum sint et ministri iustitie, et nulla secundum philosophos sit maior iustitia quam religio, qui cultus est deitatis; quo evacuato, nulla erit vera iustitia. Dico, quod principes et domini temporales tenentur vindicare malefactores, maxime contumaces et destructores christiane religionis, quia maiores peccatores esse non possunt.

Unde, licet precedere debeat doctrina et verbum, et ubi non audierint, gladius spiritualis scilicet ecclesiastica censura; tamen, si contempserint, necessarius erit gladius temporalis. Alias, cito ferre pessimi haeretici et perversi devastarent vineam Domini Sabaoth. Ideo dixit Petrus: 'Domine, ecce gladii duo hic' [Luc. 22. 38], quod de potestate spirituali et temporalis exponitur, ut, qui contempserit primum, timeat secundum. Et quis, rogo, non timet legum severitatem, dominorum vindictam? Vix de centum est unus, qui solo amore discedat a malo et faciat bonum. Omnis status, omnis conditio timore et disciplina conservatur. Neque isti schismatici, de quibus loquimur, serviunt regi et dominis nisi timore. Deus novit, quantis vexationibus exigunt ab eis tributa, sed Dei honorem non requirunt.

Debemus ergo, ubi necesse [est], eos monere, ut suos vasallos compellant ad fidem catholicam. Immo clamant leges, clamant iura reges et dominos ad extirpationem haeticorum et schismaticorum; et negligentes deponi debent a suis dignitatibus. Sic papa Zacharias ut habetur in Decretis, deposuit Lodovicum, regem Francorum, patrem Pipini. Sic Innocentius Ottonem, imperatorem, hac de causa. Unde et dominus Parisiensis [Guilelmus Arvernus] in libro De fide et legibus probat omnem sectam contrariam christianae religioni debere exterminari igne et gladio.¹³² Licet isti non indigeant tanta severitate, quia pro uno bove, quem time[n]t perdere, pro maiori parte recipiunt fidem. Ecce quam vilis coactio.

Quod autem dicitur, quod Apostoli et alii sancti isto modo non converterunt mundum inferendo violentiam, sed probatos in fide baptizabant, respondeo quod aliud tempus istud et aliud illud. Distingue tempora, et concordabis scripturas! Preterea de paganis et lupis aliud; [aliud] de istis schismaticis et ovibus errantes sciendum est. Tunc enim, vigente ubique idolatria, et in valentibus leonibus et lupis, scilicet tyrannis Romanis et idolorum cultoribus, non solum violentiam aliis inferre, sed vix per criptas latitando vivere poterant. Tunc stupentes super miraculis et tanto fervore sanctorum orientum ac vita mirabili attrahebantur investigare de eorum fide et doctrina. Sic Tristanter et alii innumerabiles. Sic Adrianus stupens interrogavit: 'Adiuro vos' etc. Modo quis meis exemplis aut miraculis trahitur. Utinam non magis retraherentur a fide nostris exemplis malis! Nec diebus illis ad ovile Christi erat aliquis recipiendus, nisi prius multis experientiis de lupo factus agnus paratus esset non solum Christi legibus subici, sed etiam pro eius nomine mori. Sed nunc quis sine gravi peccato has

involve themselves in spiritual matters; rather, prelates and religious should lead people by word and example, and, if necessary, strike the rebellious with the spiritual sword, not the secular one. For we do not find that the apostles and other saints converted people through such lords.

To this I reply that, since they are ministers of God for the punishment of evildoers and the praise of those who do good, as the Apostle clearly shows in Romans 13: 'Let every soul [be subject to higher powers. For there is no power but from God: and those that are, are ordained of God]' (Romans 13:1). Behold the Apostle's words! Likewise, Peter says in his epistle: 'Be subject [therefore to every human creature for God's sake: whether it be to the king as excelling]' (1 Peter 2:13). Because they are also ministers of justice, and according to the philosophers there is no greater justice than religion—which is the worship of divinity—and if that is destroyed, there will be no true justice at all, I say that princes and secular lords are bound to punish evildoers, especially those who are obstinate and destroyers of the Christian religion, because there can be no greater sinners than these.

Although doctrine and the word ought to come first, and if these are not heeded, the spiritual sword, namely ecclesiastical censure, and if these are despised, the temporal sword becomes necessary. Otherwise, the most wicked and perverse heretics would quickly lay waste to the vineyard of the Lord of Hosts. That is why Peter said, 'Lord, behold, here are two swords' (Luke 22:38), which is interpreted as referring to spiritual and temporal authority: so that whoever scorns the first may fear the second. And who, I ask, does not fear the severity of laws and the vengeance of lords? Scarcely one in a hundred is there who turns away from evil and does good purely out of love. Every rank and every condition is maintained by fear and discipline. Nor do these schismatics of whom we speak serve the king and their lords except out of fear. God knows by what vexations they exact tribute from them, but they do not require the honour of God.

Therefore, where it is necessary, we ought to admonish them to compel their vassals to the Catholic faith. Indeed, the laws cry out, the rights cry out, that kings and lords are bound to the extirpation of heretics and schismatics; and those who are negligent ought to be deposed from their dignities. Thus, Pope Zacharias, as is recorded in the Decretals, deposed Louis, king of the Franks, the father of Pepin. In the same way, Innocent deposed Otto the Emperor for this reason. Hence also the Master of Paris [William of Auvergne], in the book On the Faith and the Laws demonstrates that every sect contrary to the Christian religion ought to be exterminated by fire and sword.¹³² Although these men do not require such severity, since for the sake of a single ox, which they fear to lose, the greater part of them embrace the faith. Behold, how cheap is compulsion.

But as for the claim that the apostles and other saints did not convert the world in this manner by inflicting violence, but baptized those proven in the faith, I reply that our times are different from that. Distinguish the times, and you will be in agreement with the Scriptures! Moreover, one must understand one thing about pagans and wolves, and another about these schismatics and wandering sheep. For then, when idolatry was flourishing everywhere, and the Roman tyrants and the worshippers of idols were powerful, like lions and wolves, not only could they not inflict violence on others, but they could scarcely live, hiding in catacombs. Then people, struck with wonder at the miracles, at the great fervour of the saints dying, and at their marvellous way of life, were drawn to inquire into their faith and teaching, like Tristanter and countless others. Thus Hadrian, astonished, asked: 'I adjure you', and so forth. But now, who is drawn by my examples or miracles? Would that they were not rather driven away from the faith by our bad examples! Nor in those days was anyone to be received into the fold of Christ unless, through many tests, he had been made from a wolf into a lamb, ready not only to submit to the laws of Christ but even to die for his name. But now,

oves errantes perire patitur, cum potest eas ad gregem reducere, et non curat.

Tempus fuit, primo quo Ecclesia velut parvula educanda fuit lacte dulcedinis, et hoc per Christum ipso dicente: 'non possunt filii sponsi lugere' etc. [Math. 9, 15]. Tempus fuit, quo flagellis erat erudienda ut puella, ne lasciveret, et hoc in martyribus. Deinde, iam nubilis facta, cum honore ducta est ad nuptias, et hoc per Constantinum et alios Christi paranympnos. Demum, materfamilias effecta, protervos filios flagellis corrigere habet, non per se ipsam, sed per ministros sibi a Deo datos.

De aliis tribus viis successine pertranseo causa brevitatis.

II – Secundum inductivum: natura

Secundum motivum vel via inductiva huius operis est [natura] et documen[tum] naturale, insertum cuilibet homini. Si enim tanta sollicitudine ac divinis praeceptis moniti curamus subvenire nostris proximis, et ex compassione naturali movemur compatientes eorum corporalibus indigentibus, et ministramus per opera pietatis eorum corporibus utique morituris, ne pereant; quanta compassione quantaque pietate moveri debemus erga animas in aeternum vi[c]turas et subvenire, ne pereant! Unde predictus dominus Parisiensis in predicto libro de hac materia dicit: 'Quis dubitat quin morti corporali hominum tam parvulorum quam adultorum succurrendum sit, etiam eis invitis, et quin extrahendi sint de aqua et de igne ea violentia, quam requirunt ista pericula, ne in ea se precipient aut aliter cadant, sunt arcendi. Si enim morti corporali brutorum animalium tanto opere succurritur, si tanta sollicitudine extrahuntur de puteis et foveis, quanto magis ista facienda sunt, ut occurratur morti hominum corporali, ac multo fortius sunt agenda, ut occurratur morti hominum corporali, ac multo fortius sunt agenda, ut occurratur eorumdem morti spirituali. Inviti ergo et quantumlibet renitentes extrahendi sunt de periculis spiritualibus propter mortem spiritualem. Haec autem mors non est nisi vitium et peccatum, quae a Deo separant, qui est vita animarum'.¹³³ Multa alia dicit, quae causa brevitatis omitto.

III – Tertium inductivum: Scriptura

Tertium motivum est Scriptura tam novi quam veteris Testamenti. De quibus pauca noto. Probat primo nostram intencionem ille Nabugodonosor, qui ante perversus et infidelis dixit: 'Quicumque non adoraverit statuum' etc. [Dan. 3]. Deinde conversus ad Deum precepit: 'Paveant omnes habitantes in terra Deum Sydrach' etc. 'Et quicumque blasphemaverit Deum Sydrach' etc. Sic propheta David, postquam predixit tempus, in quo 'astiterunt reges terrae', scilicet Herodes et Pylatus, 'et principes', scilicet Annas et Cayphas, 'convenerunt adversus Dominum', etc. [Ps. 2.2]; persequantur primo Christum propter ydola; persequentur modo ydola propter Christum, ut omnis potestas Christo subiciatur. Nota et in evangelio parabolam de nuptiis, ubi dixit rex: 'Compelle intrare' [Luc. 14, 23]. Vide textum. Alia plura omitto.

IV – Quartum inductivum: exemplum

who can, without grave sin, allow these wandering sheep to perish when he is able to bring them back to the flock but does not care?

There was a time, first, when the Church, like a little girl, had to be nourished with the milk of sweetness—and this was through Christ himself, who said: 'Can the children of the bridegroom mourn [as long as the bridegroom is with them? But the days will come, when the bridegroom shall be taken from them, and then they shall fast]' (Matthew 9:15). There was a time when she had to be trained with whips like a young girl, lest she grow wanton, and this was in the time of the martyrs. Then, when she had already come of age, she was led with honour to marriage, and this was through Constantine and the other attendants of Christ. Finally, having become the mistress of the household, she has the duty to correct her insolent sons with whips, not by herself, but through the ministers given to her by God.

As for the other ways and paths, I pass over them briefly for the sake of conciseness.

II – The Second Inducement: Nature

The second inducement, or the inductive path of this work, is nature itself and the natural law implanted in every human being. For if, warned by such great concern and by divine precepts, we take care to help our neighbours and, moved by natural compassion, sympathize with their bodily needs, and through works of mercy serve their bodies—which are, after all, destined to die—lest they perish, with how much greater compassion and with how much greater piety ought we to be moved toward souls that will live forever, and to help them lest they be lost! Hence the aforesaid Master of Paris, in the aforementioned book on this subject, says: 'Who would doubt that help must be given to rescue human beings—both small children and adults—from bodily death, even against their will, and that they should be pulled out of water and fire with such force as these dangers require, lest they throw themselves in or otherwise fall and must be restrained? For if such effort is made to save even the bodily life of brute animals, if with such concern they are drawn out of wells and pits, how much more ought we do these things to prevent bodily death in human beings—and far more earnestly must these things be done to prevent their spiritual death. Therefore, even against their will, and however much they resist, they must be drawn out of spiritual dangers because of spiritual death. This death, moreover, is nothing other than vice and sin, which separates from God, who is the life of souls'.¹³³ He says many other things, which I omit for the sake of brevity.

III – The Third Inducement: Scripture

The third inducement is Scripture, both of the New and of the Old Testament. Of these, I note a few examples. First, that same Nebuchadnezzar proves our intention—he who at first was perverse and faithless, saying: 'Whoever does not worship the statue [shall immediately be cast into the midst of a burning fiery furnace]' (Daniel 3:6). Then, having been converted to God, he commanded: 'Let all the inhabitants of the earth fear the God of Shadrach' and: 'Whoever blasphemes the God of Shadrach [Meshach, and Abednego shall be torn limb from limb and their houses laid in ruins] (Daniel 3:28–29). Likewise, the prophet David, after he foretold the time when 'the kings of the earth stood up', namely Herod and Pilate, and 'the princes', namely Annas and Caiaphas, 'gathered together against the Lord [and against his Anointed] (Psalm 2:2). At first, they persecuted Christ on account of idols; but now they will persecute idols on account of Christ, so that all power is subjected to Christ. Note also in the Gospel the parable of the wedding feast, where the king says: 'Compel them to come in' (Luke 14:23). See the text. Many other passages I omit.

IV – The Fourth Inducement: Example

Quartum motivum est exemplum, et hoc in sanctis imperatoribus et regibus, quos Deus misit tamquam suos nuntios ad mundi conversionem. Quia, licet Apostoli seminaverunt verbum salutis per mundum, tamen propter persecutionem tyrannorum infidelium illud semen non potuit convallescere ad completam conversionem et stabilitatem sanctae Ecclesie, donec Dominus corda regnum vertit sub iugo fidei. Sic per Constantinum Latinos et Grecos, sic per Karolum Magnum Germanos et Theutonicos, sic per sanctum regem Stephanum Hungaros certe non tantum verbo, sed gladio et duris bellis convertit, cum tamen non essent haeretici vel schismatici sed penitus pagani. Sic per Ludovicum istum Comanos et Philisteos [sic] et Sclavos schismaticos ad fidem duxit, qui modo Christi gratiam gaudent. Immo et verecundantur de suo primo statu perverso.

Multa de epistolis Augustini contra Donatistas de hac materia adduci possunt, multaque de legendis Apostolorum et aliorum possent allegari, quomodo reges per eos conversi tota sua regna baptizant ad petitionem unius apostoli, qui non poterant in paucis diebus omnes de regno suo docere, ut supra obiectum fuit. Sed inter haec flendum est, quomodo imperatoris Romani et pagani centies servierunt ferventius dyabolo et ydolis suis, quam modo christiani principes Deo vivo et vero, et suae fidei gloriosae.

Probat hoc Diocletianus, qui tantummodo intra unum mensem XVII milia civium Romanorum interemit, nolentium ydola adorare. Et Maximianus sororum suam Arthemiam occidit. Aliis omissis, qui per annos CCCLX non cessaverunt fundere sanguinem christianorum. Et nostri domini huius temporis vix verbo volunt Christo servire, immo potius impediunt.

Hec predicta correctioni et emenda[tioni] maiorum simpliciter et clare [submitto]. Idcirco notavi, fratres mei, ad vestram et meam informationem, ut possitis contradicentibus resistere et rationem reddere, omni petenti, sitisque ferventiores ad conversionem istorum, de quibus diximus, pro nostra et eorum salute ad mea[m]que et vestram gloriam in die Christi.

Stephanus Papa: 'Dubius in fide infidelis est; nec ei[s] omnino credendum, qui fidem veritatis ignorant'.¹³⁴

Leo Papa: 'Qui alios, cum potest, ab errore non revocat, se ipsum errare demonstrat'.¹³⁵ Augustinus, De fide catholica: 'Firmissime tene et nullatenus dubites omnem haeticum vel schismaticum cum dia[bo]lo et eius angelis eterni ignis incendio participandum, nisi ante finem vitae catholice fuerit incorporatus et reintegratus Ecclesie'.¹³⁶ Et post pauca: 'Omni homini, qui catholice [Ecclesie] non tenet unitatem, neque baptismus neque elemosina quantumlibet copiosa, neque mors pro Christi nomine suscepta proficere poterit ad salutem'.

Lucius Papa III: Ad obedienciam.¹³⁷ Et infra: 'Universos, qui de sacramento corporis et sanguinis domini nostri Iesu Christi, vel de baptizmate, seu peccatorum confessione, matrimonio, vel reliquis ecclesiasticis sacramentis aliter sentire vel docere non metuunt, quam sacrosancta Romana Ecclesia predicat vel observat, et generaliter quoscumque Romana Ecclesia vel singuli Episcopi per dioeceses suas cum consilio clericorum, vel clerici ipsi sede vacante cum consilio si oportuerit, vicinorum Episcoporum haeticos iudicaverint, vinculo perpetuo anathematis enodamus'.¹³⁸ Et infra: 'Presenti ordinatione sanctimus, ut, quicumque fuerint manifeste in haeresi deprehensi, si clericus est vel cuiuscumque religionis umbratione fuscatus, totius ecclesiastici ordinis prerogativa nudetur, et sit omni officio et beneficio spoliatus ecclesiastico; saeculari[s] reliquatur arbitrio

The fourth inducement is an example, namely, in the holy emperors and kings whom God sent as his messengers for the conversion of the world. For although the apostles sowed the word of salvation throughout the world, yet because of the persecution of pagan tyrants, that seed could not grow to full conversion and the stability of the Holy Church until the Lord turned the hearts of kings under the yoke of faith. Thus, [the Lord converted] the Latins and Greeks through Constantine; through Charlemagne, the Germans and Teutons, and through Saint King Stephen, he converted the Hungarians, certainly not only by word but also by the sword and hard battles—although they were not heretics or schismatics but complete pagans. In the same way, through Louis, the Lord has led the Cumans, Philistines [sic], and schismatic Slavs to faith, who now rejoice in the grace of Christ. Indeed, they are even ashamed of their former perverse state.

Many things from the letters of Augustine against the Donatists could be brought forward on this matter, and many things could be cited from the legends of the Apostles and others, showing how kings were converted by them and baptized their entire kingdoms at the request of a single apostle, who could not, in just a few days, teach all the people of their realm—as was objected above. But among all these things, it must be lamented how the emperors of Rome, though pagan, served the devil and their idols a hundred times more zealously than Christian rulers now serve the living and true God and their own glorious faith.

This is proved by Diocletian, who in the space of only one month put to death seventeen thousand Roman citizens who refused to worship idols. And Maximian killed his own sister Artemia. Passing over others, who for three hundred and sixty years did not cease to shed the blood of Christians. And our rulers of our time scarcely even wish to serve Christ with a single word—indeed, rather they hinder [his cause]. All these things I simply and plainly submit to the correction and emendation of their betters.

Therefore, I have noted these things, my brothers, for your instruction and mine, so that you may be able to resist those who contradict and to give an account to everyone who asks, and so that you may be more fervent in the conversion of those of whom we have spoken—for our salvation and theirs, and for my glory and yours on the day of Christ.

Pope Stephen: 'He who is doubtful in faith is unfaithful; nor should any trust at all be placed in those who are ignorant of the faith of the truth'.¹³⁴ Pope Leo: 'The one who is able but does not recall others from error, shows that he himself is in error'.¹³⁵ Augustine, On the Catholic Faith: 'Hold most firmly and in no way doubt that every heretic or schismatic will share in the fire of eternal burning with the devil and his angels, unless before the end of life he shall have been incorporated into the Catholic Church and restored to it'.¹³⁶ And a little later: 'For any person who does not hold to the unity of the Catholic Church, neither baptism, nor almsgiving, however abundant, nor even death endured for the name of Christ will be able to profit for salvation'.

Pope Lucius III, *Ad abolendam diversarum haeresium pravitatem*,¹³⁷ and further on: 'All those who are not afraid to think or teach otherwise concerning the sacrament of the body and blood of our Lord Jesus Christ, or concerning baptism, or confession of sins, marriage, or the other ecclesiastical sacraments, than the most holy Roman Church proclaims and observes, and in general all whom the Roman Church, or individual bishops in their dioceses with the counsel of their clergy, or the clergy themselves during a vacancy of the see, with the counsel, if necessary, of neighbouring bishops, shall have judged to be heretics, we bind with the perpetual bond of anathema'.¹³⁸ And further on: 'By this present ordinance we decree that whoever shall be manifestly discovered in heresy—if he is a cleric, or ordained by any pretended religious profession—shall be stripped of all the prerogatives of ecclesiastical rank, and be deprived of every ecclesiastical office and benefice; and he shall be left to the judgment of sec-

potestatis, animadersione puniendus, nisi continuo post deprehensionem erroris' etc. Ecclesie unitatur cum congrua satisfactione. 'Laicus autem, prout dictum est, abnegata haeresi et satisfactione exhibita, confestim ad fidem confugerit orthodoxam, saecularis iudicis arbitrio reliquatur, debitam recepturus pro qualitate facinoris ultionem'. Et infra: 'Statuimus insuper, ut comites, barones, rectores et consules civitatum et aliorum locorum, iuxta commonitionem Episcoporum, prestito corporali[ter] iuramento, promittant, quod fideliter et efficaciter, cum ab eis fuerint requisiti, Ecclesiam contra haereticos et eorum complices adiuvabunt, bona fide iuxta officium et posse suum. Si vero id observare noluerint, honore, quem obtine[n]t, spolientur et ad illos nullatenus assumantur; eis nihilominus excommunicatione ligandis et terris eorum interdicto Ecclesie supponendis'.

ular power, to be punished accordingly, unless immediately upon the detection of his error he is united to the Church with appropriate satisfaction. But if a layperson, as has been said, having renounced heresy and made satisfaction, shall at once take refuge in the orthodox faith, he shall be left to the discretion of the secular judge, to receive the due punishment appropriate to the nature of the crime'. And further on: 'We furthermore decree that counts, barons, governors, and consuls of cities and other places, in accordance with the admonition of the bishops, shall, by taking a corporal oath, promise that faithfully and effectively, whenever they are required by them, they will aid the Church against heretics and their accomplices, in good faith, according to their office and their ability. But if they are unwilling to observe this, they shall be stripped of the dignity which they hold and shall in no way be appointed to such offices; and they shall likewise be bound with excommunication, and their lands shall be placed under interdict by the Church'.

Notes

- 1 Babić 1972, pp. 287–295; Тирковић 1964, p. 320; Čošković 1990, pp. 43–50; Vukšić 2005, p. 282; Špoljarić 2019, pp. 153–167.
- 2 Šanjek 2003, p. 11.
- 3 Šanjek 2003, p. 74.
- 4 Wakefield, Evans 1991, pp. 9–37.
- 5 Dautović 2021, pp. 97–125.
- 6 Šanjek 2003, pp. 16–17.
- 7 Smičiklas 1904–1934, vol. 3, p. 362.
- 8 Theiner 1859–1860, vol. 1, p. 113.
- 9 Dautović 2021, p. 106.
- 10 Тирковић 1995, p. 220; Šanjek 2003, p. 16.
- 11 This military campaign is generally considered the only crusade effectively undertaken against Bosnia. Dautović 2021, p. 112.
- 12 Šanjek 2003, p. 134.
- 13 Theiner 1859–1860, vol. 1, pp. 205–206; Mandić 1968, p. 39.
- 14 Fermendžin 1892, p. 13.
- 15 *Tam ecclesia quam diocesis Bosnensis, quae ad Romanam ecclesiam nullo medio pertinet, totaliter lapsa sit peccatis exigentibus in perfidiam heretice pravitatis.* Theiner 1859–1860, vol. 1, p. 204.
- 16 Ćirković 1987, p. 205.
- 17 Lovrenović 2005, p. 196.
- 18 Dautović 2015, pp. 127–159; Čošković 2005, pp. 58–59.
- 19 Dautović 2015, p. 129; Glušac 1924, pp. 1–55.
- 20 Rački 1869, pp. 84–179; Rački 1870, pp. 160–263; Šanjek 1976, pp. 138–50.
- 21 Тирковић 1995, p. 221; Čošković 2005, p. 10.
- 22 Džaja, Lovrenović 2007, pp. 3–14.
- 23 Тирковић 1995, p. 221.
- 24 Šidak 1977, p. 150.
- 25 Šanjek 2003, p. 333–348.
- 26 Truhelka 1911, 355–375; Fine 2007, pp. 289–293.
- 27 In his testament, Radin refers to individuals *нашега закона*, what can be translated as 'of our order'. Truhelka 1911, p. 372.
- 28 Čošković 2005, pp. 218, 368.
- 29 Čošković 2005, pp. 219–220. Innocent III wrote that Ban Kulin was 'giving them the name Christians as if they alone embodied it' (*vocans eos antonomasice christianos*), while at the abjuration of Bilino Polje, they declared that they would be no longer calling themselves Christians 'to avoid causing harm to other Christians through the exclusive use of the name' (*ne singularitate nominis alii Christianis iniuria inferatur*). Šanjek 2003, p. 72, 82.
- 30 Тирковић 1995, p. 222.
- 31 Čošković 2005, p. 156.
- 32 Mandić 1968, pp. 40–42.
- 33 Engel 2001, 163–167.
- 34 Тирковић 1990, pp. 35–36; Džambo 2022, pp. 124–125. The first known native vicar from Bosnia was Peter of Bosnia, recorded in 1477. Schmitt 1983, p. 258.
- 35 Fermendžin 1892, p. 28.
- 36 Achim 1996, pp. 398–400.
- 37 Daniel 2014, p. 132.
- 38 Engel 2001, p. 172.
- 39 Daniel 2014, p. 25.
- 40 MH, vol. 2, p. 87.
- 41 Muscat 2010, pp. 756–763.
- 42 Toldy 1862, p. 234; Romhányi 2016, p. 238; Györffy 1963, vol. 3, p. 482; Achim 1996, p. 394.
- 43 Fermendžin 1892, pp. 28–29.
- 44 Cholewicki 2023b, pp. 39–40.
- 45 In most sources, Bartholomew is called 'of Alverna', which has led to some ambiguities as to his origin. He was however called 'Bartholomeus de Tuscia' by a charter of the commune of Korčula, suggesting the locality of 'La Verna' in Tuscany, where the Friars Minor had a famous hermitage. Fermendžin 1892, p. 53.
- 46 Lasić 1962, p. 59; Fermendžin 1892, p. 36; Božićković 1935, pp. 10–13; Mandić 1968, 74–78.
- 47 Fermendžin 1892, p. 122.
- 48 Wadding 1931–1948, vol. 8 (1376), pp. 392–394.
- 49 Mandić 1968, p. 66, 78; Šanjek 2003, p. 254.
- 50 Mandić 1968, 79; Pandžić 1991, p. 248.
- 51 Mandić 1968, p. 66.
- 52 MH vol 2, p. 116.
- 53 *Wlachos scismaticos, quorum nonnulli in pascuis et tentoriis habitant, animalia, quibus habundant, pascendo, curam predicationis seu conversionis non adhibent.* MH II, p. 140.
- 54 MH II, p. 140.
- 55 *Et unum aliud in illa parte, de qua vobis videbitur pro [...] refugio et tutela.* Wadding 1931–1948, vol. 9 (1400), p. 567.
- 56 Coco 1921, pp. 258–259; Wadding 1931–1948, vol. 9 (1400), pp. 461–462; Cholewicki 2023b, p. 39.
- 57 *Quingenta milia personarum infidelium [...] ad orthodoxe fidei sinceritatem unanimiter [...] conversa fore noscantur.* Following the source from: Mandić 1979, p. 213.
- 58 Fermendžin 1892, pp. 28–29.

- 59 Šanjek 2003, p. 258.
- 60 MH, vol. 2, p. 92. The Bosnian friars were quite creative when it came to securing their sustenance, through means internal and external to Bosnia: Matanić 1960, pp. 126–127; Wadding 1931–1948, vol. 12 (1451), pp. 130–131.
- 61 *Ut dominos temporales partium earundem possitis inducere et hortari, quod sub districtione alicuius poenae corporalis vel impositionis pecuniariae subditos et vassallos suos cogant in hiis, quae animarum salutem et catholice fidei augmentum concernunt Ecclesiae et fratrum ipsorum oboedire praeceptis.* Matanić 1962, pp. 377.
- 62 Šanjek 2003, p. 259.
- 63 Kniewald 1949, pp. 144–163; Šanjek 2003, p. 266–281.
- 64 Šanjek 2003, p. 255.
- 65 On marriage according to the ‘Bosnian custom’, which clearly perplexed Bartholomew, see: Dautović 2019, pp. 113–136
- 66 *Cum multi simplices inter grecos ignorent de scismate grecorum et simpliciter confiteantur Christum et fundamentum fidei, queritur si tales saluari possunt dummodo sint baptizati uel firmiter credant se esse baptizatos.* Kniewald 1949, p. 157.
- 67 MH vol 2, p. 117.
- 68 Matanić 1962, pp. 374–378.
- 69 Fermendžin 1892, p. 36.
- 70 Wadding 1931–1948, vol. 8 (1376), pp. 392–394.
- 71 Perrone 1992, vol. 1, p. 25.
- 72 Karácsonyi 1922–1924, vol. 1, p. 312; Coco 1921, p. 250; Mandić 1968, p. 79; Perrone 1992, vol. 1, p. 22; Cevins 2008, p. 34.
- 73 Cholewicki 2023b, p. 67.
- 74 Kniewald 1949, pp. 163–169;
- 75 Lasić 1962, p. 61.
- 76 Venice, Biblioteca Marciana, Cod. Lat. II-64, 146r; Kniewald 1949, pp. 163–164.
- 77 Galamb 2017, p. 218.
- 78 Galamb 2017, p. 220.
- 79 Lasić 1962, p. 61.
- 80 Lasić 1962, pp. 62–63.
- 81 The source mentions Vidin in Bulgaria, temporarily taken by Louis I, suggesting the author did not limit himself strictly to the borders of Hungary, but also considered areas under Hungarian influence or temporary occupation.
- 82 *Aliqui propter obstinationem, aliqui propter conversationem quam habet cum Paulitinis de Wlachia et cum haereticis de Bosnia, aliqui quia non sunt inter eos pastores deputati a suis superioribus Romanis aut Hungaris episcopis.* UB Basel, A VI 15, fol. 90v.
- 83 Lasić 1962, p. 66.
- 84 *Et tot truphas super baptizando faciunt, quod christiano intelligenti abominabile est scire vel videre.* Lasić 1962, p. 66.
- 85 Lasić 1962, p. 67.
- 86 Engel 2001, p. 172.
- 87 *Bene facit rex baptizare istos Sclavos, quia nec Grecam nec Romanam formam secuntur.* UB Basel, A VI 15, fol. 93r.; Engel 2001, p. 164.
- 88 Daniel 2014, p. 131.
- 89 Lasić 1962, p. 76.
- 90 Lasić 1962, p. 74.
- 91 *Oves errantes, quae non solum vocibus sed flagellis ad ovile veri pastoris reduci habent.* Lasić 1962, p. 71.
- 92 *Quod autem dicitur, quod apostoli et alii sancti isto modo non converterunt mundum inferendo violentiam, sed probatos in fide baptizabant, respondeo, quod aliud tempus istud et aliud illud. Distingue tempora, et concordabis scripturas!* UB Basel, A VI 15, fol. 93v.
- 93 *Quia, licet Apostoli seminaverunt verbum salutis per mundum, tamen propter persecutionem tyrannorum infidelium illud semen non potuit conualescere ad completam conversionem et stabilitatem sanctae Ecclesie, donec Dominus corda regnum vertit sub iugo fidei. Sic per Constantinum Latinos et Grecos, sic per Karolum Magnum Germanos et Theutonicos, sic per sanctum regem Stephanum Hungaros certe non tantum verbo, sed gladio et duris bellis convertit, cum tamen non essent haeretici vel schismatici sed penitus pagani. Sic per Ludovicum istum Comanos et Philisteos et Sclavos schismaticos ad idem duxit, qui modo Christi gratiam gaudent. Immo et verecundantur de suo primo statu perverso.* UB Basel, A VI 15, fol. 94r.
- 94 Magina 2008, pp. 283–294; Cholewicki 2023a, p. 109; Housley 2012, pp. 30–31.
- 95 Galamb 2023, pp. 259–260.
- 96 *Eundem fratrem Ioannem de Capestrano rebaptizare, ecclesias comburere, imagines devastare, [quae] ut aiunt (quod turchi non faciunt) ignibus incenduntur.* Bullarium franciscanum, ns vol. 2, p. 89.
- 97 *Multa eis exposuit de rege Bosne, qui eadem die qua nos intrauit Albam regalem, dicens, quod ille rex erat fictus Christianus, nec in veritate erat baptizatus, imo prohibebat suos baptizari per fratres minores, qui sunt in regno suo; quod in illo regno sunt tenentes sectam Manicheorum; quod si imperator diceret illi regi, quod populus regni Bosne baptizaretur, quod in sex mensibus totus ille populus baptizaretur.* Birk 1857, pp. 676–677. Translation from: Cholewicki 2023a, p. 103.
- 98 Fermendžin 1892, 150–151.
- 99 Galamb 2015, pp. 139–146.
- 100 Kراسић 2005, p. 110; Špoljarić 2019, p. 154.
- 101 Theiner 1863, vol. 1, pp. 395–396; Theiner 1859–1860, vol. 2, p. 237.
- 102 Čošković 1988, p. 142; Theiner 1859–1860, vol. 2, p. 236; Fine 2009, p. 578.
- 103 Miklosich 1858, pp. 438–440; Fine 2007, pp. 242–243.
- 104 *Solum sit honor humanus, non adoratio, ex qua Dei contumelia subsequatur.* Farlati 1769, vol. 4, p. 257.
- 105 Bullarium franciscanum, ns vol. 1, p. 539
- 106 Mansi 1752, pp. 537–538
- 107 Čošković 2005, p. 14.
- 108 Fine 2007, p. 253
- 109 Farlati 1769, vol. 4, p. 73; Vukšić 2005, pp. 279–280.
- 110 Translation from: Grey, Faulkner 1936–1937, vol. 5, p. 366.
- 111 Šanjek 2003, pp. 114–117, 294–299.
- 112 MH vol. 2, pp. 363–364.
- 113 Špoljarić 2019, p. 161.
- 114 Šanjek 2003, pp. 118–119.
- 115 Truhelka 1911, pp. 355–375.
- 116 Wadding 1931–1948, vol. 7 (1340), pp. 273–274.
- 117 Thallóczy 1914, pp. 415–416;
- 118 Špoljarić 2019, pp. 159, 164–165.
- 119 Lovrenović 2008, p. 40.
- 120 Špoljarić 2019, p. 157.
- 121 *Sed contra hanc rationem obiciunt quidam, quod Deo non placent coacta servicia [...]. Ad hoc respondeo, quod duplex est violentia: quaedam absoluta, quaedam condicionalis. [Violentia absoluta est], verbi gratia, in proposito: Aliquis Iudaeus vel Saracenus a christianis capitur, ligatur et non consentiens, sed renitens et contradicens baptizatus violenter. Talis nec recipit sacramentum nec rem sacramenti, Ideo nec est baptismus, nec tale obsequium Deo placet, non solum suscipientium, sed neque facientium. Et de hac violentia exponi possunt omnes rationes et auctoritates magistrorum dicentium, quod nullus violenter debet baptizari. Alio modo dicitur violentia condicionalis, verbi gratia, et cum alicui proponitur talis condicio: Si non vis recipere meam fidem et baptismum, exeas regnum meum vel solvas tantum; et quod plus est, te decapitabo. Talis etiam, sic coactus, mutat voluntatem; de necessitate facit virtutem; eligit sponte baptizari, cupiens liberari a malo; dicit: Volo, toto corde recipio. Talis, etsi fecte baptizatur; licet non recipiat rem sacramenti, scilicet Christi gratiam, sed tamen sacramentum recipit, et cum christianis vivens in brevi consentiet fidei et delectabitur in sacramentorum [receptione]. Isto modo non solum schismatici, de quibus non dubium est, sed etiam Sarraceni et gentiles compelli possunt.*

- Isto modo Hungari et Alamani conversi sunt, ut dicitur. Etsi non placet Deo eorum servitium pro modo, placet postea; sed saltem obsequium facientium semper placet. UB Basel, A VI 15, fol. 91v.
 122 Lasić 1962, p. 80.
 123 Čremošnik 1955, pp. 21–24.
 124 Lasić 1962, p. 62.
 125 Turčinović 1990, p. 216.
 126 Matanić 1960, pp. 114–115.
 127 Willems 1954, Tr. 65.
 128 A common paraphrase of Romans 3:8.
 129 The text of Fulgentius of Ruspe, often misattributed to Au-

- gustine. Fraipont 1968, p. 757.
 130 Fraipont 1968, p. 757.
 131 Likely Cseri (today's Sacošu Turces), where the Bosnian friars had a convent.
 132 Thierry 1674, vol. 1, p. 4.
 133 Thierry 1674, vol. 1, p. 26.
 134 *Decretalium Gregorii IX*: V, VII, c. 1.
 135 *Decretalium Gregorii IX*: V, VII, c. 2.
 136 *Decretalium Gregorii IX*: V, VII, c. 3.
 137 *Ad abolendam diversarum haeresium pravitatem*.
 138 *Decretalium Gregorii IX*: V, VII, c. 9.

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- Achim 1996—Viorel Achim, “Ordinul franciscan în țările române în secolele XIV–XV. Aspectele teritoriale,” *Revista istorică* 5–6/7 (1996): 391–410.
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